

D3.3: Policy Roadmap

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ABSTRACT:	<p>The report provides a comprehensive overview of the regulatory challenges surrounding the field of XR, followed by recommendations for policy making (policy roadmap). It builds on the previous report (D3.2) that analysed XR-relevant EU legislations (twenty-five in total), clustered into privacy and data, intellectual property, consumer and competition law, media and online services, cybersecurity, accessibility and non-discrimination, sectoral law, technology law, and finance law. The regulatory challenges identified showed a complex and overlapping policy landscape that leaves significant uncertainties as to the implementation of key regulations. This can hinder the development of XR technologies that, although introducing novel risks in terms of privacy, security, mental and physical wellbeing, can nevertheless offer considerable benefits to the European society. The report argues for a series of regulatory and</p>
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	<p>policy initiatives in terms of clarifying the application of regulations dealing with physical injuries and accidents, long lasting consequential impairments and impacts, and use of XR hardware in healthcare. It also offers recommendations for the implementation of key regulations in terms of large-scale collection of personal data, soft biometrics, emotion data, bystander personal data, deceptive practices and unfair competition, harmful behaviour, and cybersecurity vulnerabilities. Finally, it deals with the use of AI and provides recommendations for the implementation of the AI Act in the field.</p>
Keyword List:	Extended Reality, Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, data protection, intellectual property, consumer law, cybersecurity, health law, finance law, EU law.

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Introduction

The project XR4HUMAN focuses on an ethical and human-centered development process for extended reality (XR) technologies. It involves representing industry, consumers, regulators, and academia to generate European standards for XR. As described in its basic concept, the project supports end-user decision-making and, through a focus on inclusivity, ensures that every European company and citizen has the potential to take advantage of what XR can offer. The ultimate aim of the project is to pave the way towards a strong and competitive ecosystem while building public trust and acceptance.

A key part of the project analysis is to map, examine, evaluate, and provide guidance on the related regulatory and governance issues arising in XR technologies. We set up to fulfil this objective in a three step process resulting in three specific reports. The first report provided an analysis of the use of XR technology in various sectors, including media and entertainment, work and production, marketing, healthcare, security, education, urban planning and conservation.¹ The analysis showed the potential risks and benefits associated with the development of XR technologies in these fields of application, as they are perceived by main stakeholders.

This led to a second report that reviewed the existing regulatory framework in the EU that intersects with the ethical and policy issues raised by XR technologies.² The EU laws were clustered according to their main focus: privacy and data, intellectual property, consumer and competition law, media and online services, cybersecurity, accessibility and non-discrimination, sectoral law, technology law, and finance law. The analysis highlighted the salient features of the law (scope, subjects, main provisions) and discussed its applicability to the XR sector. Challenges that XR technologies are faced with in terms of their applicability in relation to each specific law were acknowledged. Furthermore, gaps that must be dealt with to allow for a smooth adaptation to XR were identified.

This report is the final step in the process. It provides a policy roadmap for the successful adaptation of XR technologies in European society. This includes a summary of the key regulatory aspects that influence (actively or potentially) XR developments, along with recommendations for a more comprehensive policy approach in the field. The results are not only based on the state of art and regulatory analysis of the two previous reports, but also on the work in the project that deals with ethics, user rating and interoperability issues, so far as they have a direct impact in policy. As such, this report is one of the main outputs of the project that, along with the code of conduct for XR technology development, has the ambition to be incorporated in the standard corpus of any future research on XR technologies.

¹ M Ladikas, O Madeira, J Hahn, M Correa Pérez, G Caplice, A Gerasymenko, *D3.1: State-of-art in XR Policy Debates* (XR4Human, 2023), <https://zenodo.org/records/10886620> Accessed 4 September 2025.

² M Ladikas, O Madeira, J Hahn, M Correa Pérez, P Musyoki & D Somayajula, *D3.2: Regulatory Gap Analysis* (XR4Human, 2024), <https://zenodo.org/records/14045412> Accessed 4 September 2025.

Glossary

Institutions

- CJEU: Court of Justice of the European Union
- EC: European Commission
- EDPB: European Data Protection Board
- EP: European Parliament
- EU: European Union

Legislation

- AI Act: Artificial Intelligence Regulation
- AMLD: Anti-Money Laundering Directive
- AVMSD: Audiovisual Media Services Directive
- CRD: Consumer Rights Directive
- CSAR: Child Sexual Abuse Regulation
- CTR: Clinical Trials Regulation
- Data Act: Regulation on Harmonized Rules on Fair Access to and Use of Data
- DGA: Data Governance Act
- DSA: Digital Services Act
- DMA: Digital Markets Act
- EAA: European Accessibility Act
- EED: Employment and Equality Directive
- EMD: Electronic Money Directive
- ePrivacy Directive: Directive 2002/58/EC
- GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
- GPSR: General Product Safety Regulation
- MDR: Medical Device Regulation
- MiCA: Markets in Crypto-Assets Regulation
- NIS2 Directive: Network and Information Security Directive
- PLD: Product Liability Directive
- TFEU: Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
- TMR: Regulation on the EU Trademarks
- TSD: Trade Secrets Directive
- UCPD: Unfair Commercial Practices Directive
- WAD: Web Accessibility Directive

Technologies

- AI: Artificial intelligence
- AR: Augmented reality
- MR: Mixed reality
- VR: Virtual reality
- XR: Extended reality

1. Hardware usage risks

1.1. Physical injuries and accidents

XR technologies can present significant risks of physical injuries and accidents, arising from factors such as disorientation, limited spatial awareness, hardware-related hazards, and prolonged usage.³ Users may become less aware with the real-life environment around them and may harm themselves or others due to impaired senses, which can lead to collisions, falls, loss of balance, slips and trips, and injuries.⁴ These risks were recognised by the EC in its "2020 Report on the safety and liability implications of Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things and Robotics",⁵ the EC also recognised the physical and mental risks that emerging technologies can pose to users, especially for vulnerable users such as the elderly, and suggested that safety definitions within EU legislation should explicitly encompass mental health considerations.⁶

Presently, the EU has a broad consumer protection framework which could potentially address the risk of physical injuries and accidents caused in the process of using XR technologies. The now-updated GPSR obligates manufacturers of products (including XR devices such as VR headsets, AR and MR devices)⁷ placed in the EU market to ensure that are safe and traceable and that consumers are informed of associated risks.⁸ Manufacturers, importers, and distributors are required to conduct risk assessments (that include physical safety risks such as tripping hazards, head injuries, and ergonomics), ensure traceability of products, report safety concerns, allow consumers to communicate complaints or any accident/safety issue they have experienced with a product, and provide consumers with clear and accurate information regarding the product.⁹ Depending on the severity of the issue, economic operators are also under obligation to recall unsafe products or withdraw them from the market.¹⁰ In terms of liability, the EU's new PLD holds manufacturers strictly liable for damages caused by 'defective' products, and the scope of such liability extends to physical defects in the product as well as defects in the design or manufacturing process.¹¹ It empowers consumers to bring compensation claims before a national court, if they suffered damage caused by a defective product, whereby the burden of proof lays on the manufacturer to demonstrate that their product was not defective.¹² Furthermore, for XR devices or

³ n(1) s 4.2.1, 6.2; n(2) s 3.2.1.4.

⁴ European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, *Worker Exposure to Virtual and Augmented Reality and Metaverse Technologies: How Much Do We Know?* (2024)

⁵ European Commission, 'Report on the safety and liability implications of Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things and Robotics' (2020) https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/200220-ai-report_en accessed 28 August 2025.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ European Commission, 'Obligations for Businesses' *EU Safety Gate* <https://ec.europa.eu/safety-gate/#/screen/pages/obligationsForBusinesses> accessed 25 August 2025.

⁸ Emmie Hine, Isadora Neroni Rezende, Huw Roberts, David Wong, Mariarosaria Taddeo and Luciano Floridi, 'Safety and Privacy in Immersive Extended Reality: An Analysis and Policy Recommendations' (2024) 3 *Digital Society* 1 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44206-024-00114-1> accessed 25 August 2025.

⁹ n(2) s 5.3.

¹⁰ European Commission, *EU's General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR): A New Era for Consumer Protection* (15 December 2021) <https://trade.ec.europa.eu/access-to-markets/en/news/eus-general-product-safety-regulation-gpsr-new-era-consumer-protection> accessed 25 August 2025.

¹¹ TechEthos Project, *D4.1: Analysis of International and EU Law and Policy – Part III: Digital Extended Reality (XR)* (Horizon 2020 TechEthos project, Deliverable 4.1, 30 June 2022) https://www.techethos.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/TechEthos_D4.1-Intl-and-EU-legal-analysis_Part-III_XR.pdf accessed 25 August 2025.

¹² European Commission, *Liability for Defective Products* (15 April 2021) https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/free-movement-sectors/liability-defective-products_en accessed 25 August 2025.

technologies¹³ that are developed for a specific medical purpose,¹⁴ the MDR lays down obligations on such manufacturers to have a documented risk management plan, identify and analyse known and foreseeable hazards for such technologies, and eliminate or control any risks.¹⁵

In addition, to the consumer protection framework, the newly enforced Machinery Regulation can also play a role in bolstering protections against physical injuries. Primarily, the Machinery Regulation governs the design, manufacture, and placing on the market of machinery within the EU. Its primary objective is to ensure that machinery is safe for use by protecting users from hazards such as mechanical injuries, electrical dangers, and other physical risks. It sets out essential health and safety requirements that manufacturers must meet, including risk assessments, safety features, technical documentation, and conformity procedures (such as CE marking). This legal framework ensures that only safe, compliant machinery enters the EU market. This Regulation replaced the earlier Machinery Directive, primarily expanding its scope to address emergence of new digital technologies like artificial intelligence, the Internet of things and robotics, which raise new challenges in terms of product safety.

While the GPSR and PLD provide important protections against the risk of physical injuries and accidents from XR devices, they have notable gaps. The GPSR ensures that XR devices, such as headsets or haptic gloves, are designed with safety in mind to avoid physical injuries,¹⁶ and also allows for authorities to recall XR devices that have major safety concerns. However, being a product safety legislation, it does little to regulate user behaviour or environments (e.g. space for movement), which can lead to accidents like falls or injuries from disorientation. Correspondingly, the PLD allows a user to claim compensation from the manufacturer of a defective XR device, if they suffer physical injury (e.g. neck pain or a fall caused by a malfunctioning VR headset). However, the PLD struggles in cases where XR devices have complex hardware-software integration issues, whereby the damage may arise due to either software bugs, hardware defects, or design flaws. Respectively, assigning damage due to a particular defect may be difficult to prove. Additionally, the PLD does not address injuries arising from user behaviour caused by misuse or other user actions, like tripping over cables, motion sickness, eyestrain from prolonged use, etc. The MDR applies to medical XR devices but focuses more on medical effectiveness and overall safety rather than specific physical injury prevention, lacking requirements for impact protection or collision avoidance in XR environments. It is then evident that these regulations fail to fully address risks arising from user behaviour, misuse, or the dynamic nature of immersive XR experiences.¹⁷

The Machinery Regulation lays down obligations for manufacturers of 'machinery', broadly defined as "an assembly, fitted with or intended to be fitted with a drive system other than directly applied human or animal effort, consisting of linked parts or components, at least one of which moves, and which are joined together for a specific application.". While XR devices such as VR headsets, AR glasses, or haptic suits may not resemble traditional machinery, some devices such as VR-integrated training simulators, and the Omni-directional treadmill incorporating VR for physical rehabilitation, may fall under the Regulation's

¹³ See for instance, Sympatient GmbH, 'VR-therapy software for anxiety disorders' EUDAMED DI: PP123321.T.A.74 / IFA; Superscript, 'New rules for digital mental health tech companies' <https://gosuperscript.com/news-and-resources/new-rules-digital-mental-health-tech-companies> accessed 25 August 2025.

¹⁴ n (2) s 10.

¹⁵ Joseph Peter Salisbury, 'Using Medical Device Standards for Design and Risk Management of Immersive Virtual Reality for At-Home Therapy and Remote Patient Monitoring' (2021) 6 *JMIR Biomedical Engineering* e26942 doi:10.2196/26942 accessed 25 August 2025.

¹⁶ Michele M O'Neill and Mark L Campbell, 'Using Medical Device Standards for Design and Risk Management of Immersive Virtual Reality for At-Home Therapy and Remote Patient Monitoring' *PMC* <https://doi.org/10.3390/jsc8110098> accessed 25 August 2025.

¹⁷ Caterina Rechichi, Gilda Mojà and Pasquale Aragona, 'Video Game Vision Syndrome: A New Clinical Picture in Children?' (2017) 54 *Journal of Pediatric Ophthalmology and Strabismus* 1 <https://doi.org/10.3928/01913913-20170510-01> Accessed 25 August 2025.

scope if they meet these broad criteria. It requires that manufacturers perform a comprehensive risk assessment during design and production, evaluating not just immediate mechanical risks, but also risks from the reasonably foreseeable misuse of machinery. For XR devices, this could involve identifying and mitigating risks like physical injuries, motion sickness, musculoskeletal disorders from prolonged use, vision strain, or collision hazards.¹⁸

1.2. Long-lasting consequential impairments and impacts

There are several ergonomic effects of XR use, ranging from fatigue due to hardware weight, neck and back strain from the need for more head movement, as well as eye-strain and myopia that might develop due to extended use.¹⁹ The speedy development of XR technologies produces unknowns in respect to long term effects are yet to be discovered.

As stated previously, the GPSR imposes obligations on manufacturers to ensure that they place safe products on the market,²⁰ and take corrective measures if it is proven that a product is dangerous.²¹ The risk assessments manufacturers are required to undertake extend beyond analysing risks posed in a product's normal use, to 'reasonably foreseeable conditions of use', and such products must be consistent with a "high level of protection of the health and safety of consumers."²² It also gives national authorities the power to take corrective measures including recalling²³ or withdrawing²⁴ a product reported as 'dangerous'.²⁵ In addition, the new PLD which now applies to software and AI systems,²⁶ imposes strict liability on manufacturers for the damage (including chronic or long-term physical damage) caused to consumers due to a 'defective' product and entitles them to compensation. A 'defective' product is one which does not provide the safety which a person is entitled to expect, *taking all circumstances into account*.²⁷ With the new PLD, 'defective' also extends to defects that became apparent after the release of a product, as a result of updates, upgrades or a machine-learning feature.²⁸ In terms of cybersecurity, the NIS2 Directive aims to strengthen cybersecurity resilience across essential and important sectors in the EU, by introducing stricter risk management obligations, incident reporting requirements, and enforcement measures.²⁹ Furthermore, for XR devices or technologies used in the workplace, the EED is relevant, as it aims to combat discrimination on the grounds of, *inter alia*,

¹⁸ Regulation (EU) 2023/1230 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 June 2023 on machinery and repealing Directive 2006/42/EC and Council Directive 73/361/EEC, OJ L 165, 29 June 2023, pp 1-102.

¹⁹ For a detailed understanding, you may refer to our previous reports titled D2.2 and D3.1.

<https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

²⁰ Art 5, GPSR

²¹ Art 9(8)(a), GPSR

²² Art 3(1), GPSR

²³ Article 3(25) of the GPSR defines 'recall' as 'any measure aimed at achieving the return of a product that has already been made available to the consumer'.

²⁴ Article 3(26) of the GPSR defines 'withdrawal' as 'any measure aimed at preventing a product in the supply chain from being made available on the market'.

²⁵ Article 3(3) defines a 'dangerous' product 'as any product which is not a 'safe' product.'

²⁶ European Commission, "Liability for defective products: Software and AI systems" (Single Market – Goods, Free Movement, European Commission, 8 months ago) https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/free-movement-sectors/liability-defective-products_en#software-and-ai-systems accessed 25 August 2025.

²⁷ Article 6, PLD

²⁸ n(26).

²⁹ See n(2).

disability, age or sexual orientation in regards employment and occupation.³⁰ Article 5 of the EED specifically obligates employers to make reasonable accommodations for persons with disabilities, and to take appropriate measures, where needed, to enable a person with a disability to have access to, participate in, or advance in employment, or to undergo training, unless such measures would impose a disproportionate burden on the employer. It extends the right to avail judicial, conciliation and administrative procedures, to persons that are wronged by failure of employees to apply the principle of equal treatment to them.³¹ Member States are permitted to adopt measures to prevent or compensate for disadvantages based on protected grounds, and it encourages health and safety actions that support the inclusion of disabled persons in the workplace.³² In the context of XR technologies made specifically for medical purposes, the CTR and the MDR lay down certain requirements. We have delved into the application of this regulation to XR used as medical devices in our section below.

The GPSR focuses on product design and manufacturing and can ensure that XR devices and technologies (such as VR headsets and AR glasses) meet basic safety standards before entering the market. This extends to assessing long-term harms such as musculoskeletal strain from prolonged headset use, vision issues or eye fatigue, and balance disorders or long-term spatial disorientation that might develop with repeated or prolonged XR use. It primarily functions as a preventive and reactive mechanism—recalling dangerous products after harm occurs—without offering users compensation for long-term injuries. While such recalling/withdrawing provisions do attempt to reduce widespread harm, it is an ex-post measure and does little to alleviate the damage caused to users who have witnessed the long-term impacts before knowing the dangers of using the device. It also requires users to prove that the long-term impact they experience, stems solely from an XR device that does not meet the expected safety requirements. However, in situations where there is an underestimation of health hazards that eventually materialize and harm user, the causal relationship between XR device (that may be AI-powered) and the harm caused to the user cannot easily be ascertained and demonstrated. If the process leading to the injury cannot be explained (beyond common sense), it may not be satisfactorily proven.³³

Additionally, since it is a ‘general’ legislation, the safety obligations imposed by the GPSR does not stipulate measures to combat risks posed specifically by XR devices or technologies, such as ergonomic safety mandates, exposure limits, or injury tracking systems. In this manner, the GPSR could possibly fall short in effectively addressing long-term health risks, such as musculoskeletal injuries eye strain, and myopia progression. On the other hand, if an XR device (VR headset, AR glasses, haptic gloves, or other XR hardware) has a manufacturing defect, or, lacks adequate safety warnings, has design flaws, faulty calibration system, faulty control applications or other defective software or hardware that causes physical strain or other long-term impacts due to faulty design, the PLD holds manufacturer strictly liable, and entitles users to claim compensation. However, it only applies in situations where effects arise due to an XR device or technology being defective and does not address impacts arising by user behaviour.

On the cybersecurity front, the NIS2 Directive tries to mitigate cyberattacks that can lead to long-term effects such as chronic stress injuries, eye strain, prolonged exposure risks (disorientation, seizures, balance issues) resulting from distorted visuals, malfunctioning haptics or hacked virtual environments. However, XR devices and technologies used privately (such as for gaming) fall outside the scope unless tied to critical infrastructure.

³⁰ Article 1, EED

³¹ Article 9, EED

³² Article 7, EED

³³ R Vecellio Segate and A Daly, ‘Encoding the Enforcement of Safety Standards into Smart Robots to Harness Their Computing Sophistication and Collaborative Potential: A Legal Risk Assessment for European Union Policymakers’ (2024) 15(3) *European Journal of Risk Regulation* 665, doi:10.1017/err.2023.72 accessed 25 August 2025.

Specifically for XR devices and technologies used in the workplace, the EED may apply in situations where the long-term use of XR devices causes or worsens an employee's pre-existing physical condition or disproportionately harms a particular group. If the employer fails to consider or mitigate such harms and an employee suffers physical consequences due to such inaction, the employee may challenge this inaction on the basis of their rights being ignored.³⁴ It also encourages employers to implement XR-specific workplace protections or training programs to reduce adverse impacts on vulnerable groups (e.g. ergonomic assessments, usage limits). It allows employees with disabilities who suffer physical consequences from XR use, to challenge such employer inaction to account, for such consequences, on the person with disability, if reasonable accommodations were not made in light of their obligations under Article 5. While the EED can indirectly address some long-term physical impacts of XR in employment contexts, particularly where those impacts relate to disability or unequal treatment, it is not a product safety law and cannot, on its own, ensure comprehensive protection from long-term XR hardware risks across the whole society. These risks were recognised by the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work. Their analysis points out that immersive virtual environments can lead to physical and ergonomic risks, including cybersickness, visual strain, musculoskeletal disorders, and increased risk of falls, due to reduced situational awareness. They also note the lack of data on the long-term impacts of XR use in work environments, which complicates efforts to prevent and manage these risks.⁹⁹

Supplementing these legislations is the Machinery Regulation, which enforces a safety-by-design approach, requiring manufacturers to integrate ergonomics and prevent strain or fatigue during extended use. This is particularly applicable to wearable XR devices which make direct contact with users and may cause repetitive stress injuries or sensory overload. Additionally, the Regulation obliges manufacturers to provide clear, accessible instructions and warnings, which must include information on residual risks, appropriate usage time, and potential adverse effects, ensuring users are aware of long-term safety considerations.

While these legislations address aspects of long-term physical risks from XR technologies, they do so in a fragmented way. The GPSR ensures basic product safety but lacks XR-specific protections and offers no user compensation. The PLD allows compensation for harm caused by defective devices, but only where a defect is clearly identifiable. NIS2 helps prevent cyber-related physical harm but excludes privately used XR devices. The EED offers some workplace protections, especially for vulnerable groups, but is limited in scope. The CTR and MDR provide stronger safeguards for medical XR devices, including lifecycle monitoring and risk mitigation, but do not extend these to consumer or enterprise XR products. Together, these laws offer partial coverage, but some regulatory gaps remain—especially for non-medical, everyday XR use.

1.3. Cybersickness

³⁴ European Commission, *Employment Equality Directive 2000/78/EC* (European Commission, Policies and Activities – Rights at Work) https://employment-social-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies-and-activities/rights-work/tackling-discrimination-work/legislation-employment-equality-directive-200078ec_en Accessed 25 August 2025.

A primary hardware related risk related to XR devices and technologies is that of cybersickness, or simulation sickness,³⁵ where users of immersive XR experience a series of negative symptomatology including, but not limited to, nausea, vomiting, eyestrain, disorientation, ataxia, and vertigo.³⁶

The prevailing laws that could potentially address this issue are the GPSR, PLD, CTR and MDR. Principally, the GPSR mandates that products must be safe for consumer use, considering all associated risks. In addition to the relevant provisions captured above, the revised PLD broadens the definition of "product" to include software and digital products, recognizing damages from defects that cause personal injury. In addition, specifically with respect to XR devices made for medical purposes, the CTR mandates clinical trials to ensure safety of the product and requires comprehensive risk assessments, whereas the MDR requires manufactures to implement risk management measures throughout the XR device's lifecycle.

While the GPSR requires manufacturers to evaluate and mitigate known risks to ensure product safety, the absence of explicit references to cybersickness in the regulation makes it an implicit safety risk which manufacturers would still be expected to account for in their risk assessments, because it is a known and foreseeable effect of the product. Even when the industry practice is to include this risks in documentation, we believe it is important that is explicit in the law. Under the updated PLD, if an XR device is found to cause cybersickness due to defects, affected individuals may seek compensation from the product's manufacturers or importers. Especially for XR technologies classified as medical devices undergoing clinical trials, the CTR mandates evaluation of all potential risks, including cybersickness, and the MDR obligates manufacturers to identify, assess, and mitigate risks, including cybersickness, throughout the lifecycle of the device. While existing EU law like the GPSR, PLD, CTR, and MDR offer mechanisms to address cybersickness in specific contexts, some gaps remain. The GPSR lacks explicit provisions for cybersickness, making its application to XR technologies only implicit. The PLD offers post-incident compensation but does not proactively prevent cybersickness. The CTR and MDR effectively address cybersickness in medical contexts but do not extend it to consumer XR products. This fragmented regulatory landscape indicates a need for more comprehensive and explicit guidelines to effectively mitigate cybersickness risks across all XR technologies.

1.4. Use and handling of XR hardware in healthcare

Using XR devices and technologies for medical purposes presents novel challenges. Risks range from routine issues such as disinfection of VR equipment (especially in hospitals), to issues such as skin irritation, allergies and visual fatigue.³⁷

With respect to addressing the use and handling of XR devices as medical devices, the GPSR and PLD lay down general safety obligations for XR device manufacturers, whereas sector-specific legislations such as CTR and MDR stipulate specific requirements for medical devices (including XR devices manufactured for medical purposes, such as VR headsets). To ensure the safety of medical devices, the CTR requires manufacturers to conduct clinical trials, and to ascertain that they are safe, ethical, and scientifically sound. The CTR imposes strict instructions on the pre-registration of a clinical trial as well as precise

³⁵ For a detailed understanding, you may refer to our previous reports titled D2.2 and D3.1. <https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

³⁶ E Chang, H-T Kim and B Yoo, 'Virtual Reality Sickness: A Review of Causes and Measurements' (2020) 36 *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction* 1, doi:10.1080/10447318.2020.1778351 Accessed 25 August 2025.

³⁷ For a detailed understanding, you may refer to our previous reports titled D2.2 and D3.1. <https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

instructions on protocol, data protection, study design, reporting obligations and compensation for damages.³⁸ In addition, the MDR, *inter alia*, imposes stricter safety and performance checks for medical devices before approval, and requires manufacturers to monitor long-term risks and adverse effects even after devices are put out into the market.³⁹ The GPSR applies to consumer products, including medical devices when specific sectoral legislation does not provide comprehensive safety requirements, and the PLD holds producers liable for damage caused by defects in their products, including medical devices.

For XR devices intended for medical use, the CTR and the MDR together offer a structured approach to managing long-term physical risks. Under the MDR,⁴⁰ devices intended for reuse must be designed to allow safe cleaning, disinfection, and sterilization. This ensures that XR headsets can be properly disinfected between uses, addressing infection control concern. Additionally, manufacturers are required to establish and maintain a risk management system, identifying and mitigating risks associated with device use, which encompasses both minor and significant risks in medical practice. The CTR ensures that clinical trials evaluate not only immediate effects but also longer-term impacts such as musculoskeletal strain, visual fatigue, and psychological effects, while also requiring informed patient consent. However, once the device is released, the CTR does not provide a mechanism for compensating patients who suffer long-term harm. The MDR addresses this gap by requiring manufacturers to assess and monitor risks throughout the entire product lifecycle and to take corrective actions if users experience long-term physical or neurological impairments. Yet, both regulations apply only to medical XR devices—leaving consumer, industrial, and educational XR applications outside their protective scope.

While the CTR does not explicitly address device disinfection or specific product risks, it requires that all aspects of participant safety be considered, which would include ensuring that XR devices used for medical purposes do not pose undue risk. The general regulations such as the GPSR mandate that products placed on the market must be safe, considering all relevant aspects, including the product's characteristics and the specific needs of vulnerable consumers, and has provisions for recalling/withdrawing dangerous products. This broad requirement can encompass concerns like device disinfection and safe usage in medical settings.⁴¹ Lastly, under the PLD, if a defect in an XR headset used in healthcare causes harm, whether from inadequate disinfection leading to infection or a malfunction during medical procedure, the manufacturer can be held liable, and the user can demand compensation.

Collectively, these regulations provide a framework addressing both routine and significant risks associated with XR headsets in healthcare. The MDR offers detailed requirements for device safety, including disinfection and risk management. The GPSR ensures general product safety, supplementing areas not explicitly covered by the MDR. The PLD provides a mechanism for compensation in cases of harm due to product defects. However, the CTR's applicability is limited to clinical trials involving medicinal products and does not directly address medical devices. While the existing regulations cover many aspects of safety and liability, there may be gaps in specific guidance for emerging technologies like XR headsets, particularly concerning standardized disinfection protocols and real-time risk assessment during medical procedures.

³⁸ See n(2).

³⁹ See n(2)

⁴⁰ Annex I, Chapter II, Section 10.4, MDR.

⁴¹ Reuschlaw, 'Does the Product Safety Regulation Apply to Medical Devices?' (Reuschlaw, 19 June 2023) <https://www.reuschlaw.de/en/news/does-the-product-safety-regulation-apply-to-medical-devices/> Accessed 25 August 2025.

1.5. Use in life-threatening situations

As highlighted above, the use of XR devices and technologies give rise to several ergonomic effects, from fatigue due to hardware weight, strain from requiring more head movement, but also movement limitations. These injuries may be usually minor but at times they might be life-threatening or even result in death. These situations can include suicidal ideation,⁴² risk of falling from heights, or clinical emergencies where XR is used either as a tool (e.g. exposure therapy) or is implicated in exacerbating harm (e.g. immersion-related disorientation).⁴³

Currently, the risk of XR devices and technologies leading to a life-threatening situation can be regulated under product safety law, medical device safety laws, as well as under the new AI Act. As captured above, the GPSR requires that products (including XR headsets) be safe under normal and reasonably foreseeable conditions of use, especially considering vulnerable users.⁴⁴ In a similar manner, the PLD would cover situations when a defect in the XR device (hardware or software) causes harm, including death or injury. The AI Act aims to categorize AI systems according to the level of risk they pose to health, safety, and fundamental rights of individuals. This classification into risk levels in turn determines the regulatory requirements that then apply. Primarily, Article 5(1)(a) of the AI Act prohibits AI systems that manipulate behaviour in ways that can lead to physical or psychological harm, especially targeting vulnerable groups (e.g. children, patients, etc.). AI systems used in critical areas such as healthcare, public safety, and emergency response are considered "high-risk", which results in the obligation to conduct continuous risk management, including identification and mitigation of known and foreseeable risks, and the consideration of risks to health and safety during normal use, misuse, and foreseeable abuse. This extends to post-market monitoring to continuously evaluate and respond to real-world risks, including those not captured in lab testing or trials—vital for spotting rare but dangerous incidents involving XR-induced psychological or physical harm. In addition, users of a high-risk AI system must be informed how the system works, what its limitations are, and how to safely operate it, which is critical in emergencies where incorrect assumptions could worsen outcomes. Additionally, high-risk XR systems must be designed so that human oversight is always possible, allowing clinicians, caregivers, or users to interrupt, override, or shut down the system if it creates a life-threatening risk.

While the GPSR allows for market surveillance and recalls of hazardous XR hardware/software, it does not mandate specific safety designs for psychological/immersion-related harms or life-threatening scenarios. The PLD applies when a defect in the XR device (hardware or software) causes harm, including death or injury, but it is only triggered after the damage occurs, which does little to prevent life-threatening risks. The AI act ensures that XR systems that incorporate AI-driven persuasive design, neurological manipulation, or adaptive feedback loops (e.g. for behavioural change or exposure therapy) must not exploit user vulnerabilities. Systems that could subliminally distort human behaviour in ways that cause "significant harm" will be banned (Article 5(1)(a)). This could offer protection from manipulation in XR, but that depends on how "significant harm" is interpreted.⁴⁵ AI systems embedded in XR technologies for diagnostic, therapeutic, monitoring, or triage purposes (such as mental health therapy

⁴² MH Ronaghi and M Ronaghi, 'How Does Virtual Reality Technology Affect Suicidal Ideation in Society?' (2025) 34(1) *International Journal of Mental Health Nursing* e13443, doi:10.1111/inm.13443 accessed 28 August 2025.

⁴³ A Rizzo and S Koenig, 'Is Clinical Virtual Reality Ready for Primetime?' (2017) 31 *Neuropsychology* 877, doi:10.1037/neu000405 accessed 25 August 2025. For a detailed understanding, you may refer to our previous reports titled D2.2 and D3.1.

⁴⁴ Article 5 and 6, GPSR

⁴⁵ E Hine, I N Rezende, H Roberts, D Wong, M Taddeo and L Floridi, 'Safety and Privacy in Immersive Extended Reality: An Analysis and Policy Recommendations' (2024) 3 *Digital Society* 1, doi:10.1007/s44206-024-00114-1 accessed 28 August 2025.

or clinical simulations) can fall into the category of 'high risk' if the failure or malfunction of the system could lead to serious harm or death. The current regulatory framework does regulate the risk of life-threatening situations specifically when it comes to XR devices used for medical purposes and those that have an AI system integration. However, there are some gaps when XR is used outside clinical or certified medical contexts (e.g. consumer XR wellness apps), and when the XR device is lacking AI components (thereby evading AI Act safeguards). Additionally, it also falls short where XR devices or technologies are deployed in psychologically sensitive or life-threatening scenarios (e.g. apps used during mental health crises) where user harm is not foreseeable under traditional product safety lenses.

2. Data issues

2.1. Large-scale collection of personal data

XR applications are by default dealing with large scale of data, whether personal or not. A key part of their development process is to identify user needs and create products that fulfil them, whether these refer to physical or psychological needs. Processing large-scale data is an essential part in this process⁴⁶. As we have discussed previously,⁴⁷ XR technologies have a unique ability to gather directly and indirectly a multitude of data from individuals at high speed and accuracy. In case of personal data or anonymised individual data that can nevertheless potentially reveal personal data are being collected, a number of challenges have been identified. Some regulatory challenges that ought to be addressed refer to key European regulations.

Foremost amongst them is the GDPR, the main EU personal data protection law that has been in effect since 25 May 2018. The GDPR has been designed to give citizens more control over how their data is collected, processed, and protected online, binding organisations to strict rules on accumulating and processing of personal data. It provides details on the mandatory use of technical safeguards (e.g. data encryption) and requires a demanding level of justification for personal data collection. GDPR is a very comprehensive legislation and levies heavy penalties on organisations that break its requirements: up to 4 per cent of the organisations' global annual revenue or €20 million, whichever is higher.

It is clear that so long as personal data is gathered (directly or indirectly) via XR devices and software within the EU, GDPR is fully applicable for developers, even when based outside the EU. This is irrespective of the setting, the reason for data gathering, or the aim of the XR device use (e.g. for research, entertainment, surveillance, etc). All the compliance requirements of GDPR are in full force and organisations and businesses that use XR devices are liable to penalties as stipulated in the legislation. Even if the intention of the XR application is not to gather personal data, it is highly probable that most applications have nevertheless the potential to do so, and the onus to prove otherwise lies with the developer.

This brings into the forefront GDPR obligations such as the establishment of a position of data protection officer, data minimisation, implementation of data risk assessments, awareness raising, training and cooperation with the supervisory authority. Data minimisation obligations, if properly applied, would require XR devices not to gather any additional personal data other than the strictly necessary ones. However, even if the obligation is followed, it does not mean that sensitive personal data cannot be inferred through the use of the devices (e.g. soft biometrics, inferences of health status, inferences of emotional conditions, etc.).

At the same time, it is unclear in the GDPR whether a data protection officer position is required for XR SMEs that do claim not to process large-scale of personal data (normally, such data will be collected by the device manufacturers), since the regulation is not well-defined on this issue. Unlike the DSA that defines platform size in strict terms, GDPR does not define large-scale data. In addition, XR developers could be required to ensure the "right to be forgotten" by allowing for erasure of data that are either

⁴⁶ Large-scale or big data, is difficult to define precisely. They depend on Volume (amount of data), Velocity (speed of analysis) and Variety (many forms). Although XR applications do not necessarily fulfill the prerequisite of Volume, they certainly fulfill the Velocity and Variety aspects.

⁴⁷ n (1), S 3.

personal in nature, or have the ability to be so⁴⁸. This is a grey area as well, since XR devices might gather anonymised data that have the potential to lead to personal identification (e.g. gate movement) but cannot be easily detached from the data corpus.

Another related regulation is the ePrivacy Directive that deals with digital technologies and in particular with applications on digital communications. It covers the right to privacy and confidentiality concerning the accumulation and processing of personal data in electronic communications. Despite the obvious overlap with GDPR, the ePrivacy Directive focuses on the area of communication, making it a unique contribution to the challenges faced by new technologies such as XR. Once the concept of electronic communication services is extended to instant messaging applications, exchanges between users (e.g. conversations between players) in an XR environment will fall under this Directive and the forthcoming regulation deriving from it.⁴⁹ XR services will need to meet the criteria of not being a “minor and purely ancillary feature to another service” to be considered an electronic communication service. Very specific cases of XR applications will certainly meet this criterion (e.g. VRChat, Resonite, Engage, Banter, Spatial, Arrival.Space, Gorilla Tag, etc.). This means that XR providers will need to meet retention, security and traffic requirements under the ePrivacy Directive. In addition, the use of cookies in XR applications for functional and marketing purposes must be used upon the user's or subscriber's explicit consent to the service. The fact that XR devices can, in principle, collect special categories of personal data (e.g. biometrics) can complicate the use of cookies and shows a current gap in the Directive.

Furthermore, large-scale data follow under the realm of the Data Act that aims to increase fairness in the digital environment by enhancing data access and distribution. The Data Act encourages data-driven innovation by enabling individuals and businesses to access and share the data they generate, with appropriate safeguards. This legal framework promotes fairness, transparency, and interoperability in data use, complementing the principles of the GDPR where personal data is involved. For XR developers, this means that they can potentially access more data generated by connected products and services, including IoT devices. This broader access can lead to better insights into user profiles and enhance innovation in XR applications. It can create advantages for XR developers as they can benefit by leveraging diverse data sources to enhance their applications, create more immersive experiences, and improve user interactions.

Since the Data Act does not differentiate between the amount of data in its sharing arrangements, it can benefit smaller developers by allowing them access to data they wouldn't otherwise be able to acquire. On the other hand, Big-Tech companies still hold a great advantage by monopolising the data market with their exceptional global access. Although the Data Act is trying to create a level playing field in data access, it is doubtful that the first-mover advantage that the Big-Tech enjoys will be reversed in the foreseeable future. The Data Act does not provide timelines for data sharing, and the precautions that data intermediaries must take mean possible delays in data access for smaller players. In addition, the Data Act puts a lot of emphasis on privacy and data security by creating significant obligations for data use and considerable punishments for breaches and misuse⁵⁰. XR developers must be aware of these aspects and adapt their businesses accordingly. This can result in substantial additional expenditure, particularly for smaller developers.

The Data Act overlaps considerably with the GDPR in issues of privacy, consent, user rights, and notifications. It works in tandem with it while focusing on data access and data governance issues. XR

⁴⁸ There is nevertheless the case that the developers and owners of XR applications might not collect any information themselves. The distribution platform might also collect data about users.

⁴⁹ n (1) S 3.2,

⁵⁰ Section 3.3, D3.2: Regulatory Gap Analysis (2024), The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project. <https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

developers can benefit directly from the Data Act by ensuring the above aspects are dealt with correctly (e.g. by establishing a Data Protection Officer position, as per GDPR) while working together with the data governance board of the Data Act to ensure fair access to datasets. For this to take effect for smaller developers, a stricter sharing timeline must be enforced by the Data Act.

Similarly, the DMA aims to ensure a level playing field for the markets in the digital sector in general, and for users of large online companies in particular. The DMA establishes the conditions for large online providers to be recognised as ‘gatekeepers’ by the EC, gives them specific obligations and prohibitions, and empowers the EC to enforce the regulation and impose remedies. Although not yet the case, several types of core platform services related to XR, such as online social networking, virtual assistant, online advertising, and online intermediation services, could fall under the DMA. In such cases, obligations restricting the sharing of data (even within services of the same company), guaranteeing device neutrality (by opening up services to competition), and ensuring interoperability (by allowing third party integration to core platform services) are enforced.

At present not many XR companies fall under DMA as gatekeepers and there are certain loopholes in the regulation that allow big tech to avoid this, by for instance creating smaller XR subsidiaries with a lower number of subscribers⁵¹. If on the other hand, big companies involved in XR such as Meta, Google, Microsoft and Apple, will be eventually considered gatekeepers (in the DMA terminology), there are significant repercussions for the accumulation and processing of data via their XR devices and related services. This is a key point relating to XR that DMA must clarify.

One should also consider in this respect the AI Act, which is the first world-wide regulatory framework for AI, aiming to foster human-centric and trustworthy AI, via a risk based approach whereby applications are assigned a risk factor (unacceptable risk, high risk, limited risk, minimal risk) that leads to specific regulatory requirements. AI powered XR applications fall under the auspices of the AI Act and must follow the relevant obligations⁵².

Regardless of the level of risk involved, any use of AI requires from the XR developer a description of the functions of algorithms in term of robustness, transparency and reliability. Depending on the risk assigned to the specific application, further obligations in terms of the safety and security of the system, including undertaking detailed impact assessment processes, are envisaged in the AI Act.

A particular grey area for XR is the prohibited AI applications that focus on “harmful manipulation and deception” as well as “emotional recognition” (see section 3.4 below). The description of such systems points to the potential of some VR applications for subliminal manipulation. At the same time, the bulk of XR applications for personal entertainment could be argued to involve deployment of subliminal techniques or purposefully manipulative or deceptive techniques⁵³, that are considered “unacceptable risks” in the AI Act. Similarly, inference of emotions in XR applications deployed at workplace or in education, might be an integral part of an application that aims at increased awareness or wellbeing. Again, these are unacceptable risks in the AI Act. Even if one classifies these risks as “high” there is a

⁵¹ n(1), S 6.3.

⁵² According to the AI Act (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>) an “AI system” means a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments. With this in mind, most XR applications are or will fall as they develop, in the realm of the AI Act.

⁵³ This presupposes a wider definition of “manipulation” and “deception”, that includes the notion of “make believe”, inherent in every VR environment. It’s important to note here that the lack of proof of malicious intent, does not exempt the application.

number of high-cost and time-consuming obligations for developers involving risk management, data governance, technical documentation, conformity assessment, EU database registration and post-market monitoring, to be followed. It is vital for XR developers that this aspect of the AI Act be fully clarified.

Finally, the CRD aims at achieving a high level of consumer protection across the EU and promote laws, regulations and administrative provisions concerning contracts concluded between consumers and traders. It has been updated to address digital content and services, which are integral to XR technologies, by extending consumer protection to digital content, ensuring that consumers have rights similar to those for physical goods. For XR technologies, this means that software updates, digital environments, and virtual goods must meet the standards promised at the point of sale, and consumers must have recourse if these standards are not met.

Although the CRD is relevant to XR applications in terms of the obligations it promotes for information requirements and transparency, rights of withdrawal and unfair contract terms, it's the data protection obligations that are most relevant here. Since pre-ticked boxes do not constitute valid consent (under GDPR), this implies that XR companies cannot assume blanket consent for data collection through default settings. Furthermore, users must be given clear information about the duration of cookie operation (in e.g. browser based webXR sites) and whether third parties have access to the data. For XR, this principle would extend to informing users about the types of data collected (e.g. biometric, movement, environmental) and for how long it is retained.

Consent requirements apply even if the information stored or accessed is not consisting of personal data. This is particularly relevant for XR, where some collected data might not be deemed "personal" but could become so when combined with other data or analysed further. Finally, users must be informed about which third-party developers or services might access data collected through a platform. XR companies must provide clear, accessible information about how personal data will be used, stored, and shared, and ensure that consumers can easily access and control their data. The CRD is therefore an integral part of the data processing aspect of XR application and developers must also understand XR applications as any other services contract. Once this is done, there are no further unclarities in the CRD.

2.2. Biometric and other sensitive data processing

Biometric data is personal data resulting from specific technical processing relating to the physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics of a natural person, which allow or confirm the unique identification of that natural person, under the GDPR⁵⁴. The range of biometrics includes fingerprints, facial recognition, iris or retina scans, voice recognition, DNA, or even gait style.

Biometric data is regulated under the GDPR as a *special category of data*. Special categories of data – also known as sensitive data – are personal data that are given higher protection under the GDPR for its potential impact on fundamental rights and freedoms, also including racial and ethnic origin, political opinion, religious and philosophical beliefs, health data, and sexual orientation⁵⁵. The processing of sensitive data (including biometric data) is in principle prohibited, and shall only be done in the specific basis provided by the GDPR, including explicit consent for one or more specific purposes⁵⁶.

⁵⁴ Article 4(14), GDPR.

⁵⁵ Article 9(1), GDPR.

⁵⁶ Article 9(2)(a), GDPR.

Although XR applications rarely, if at all, aim at gathering biometric or any other sensitive data at present, it is possible that they can process such data by design, particularly in the future. For instance, XR devices can potentially gather data such as iris scans or gait styles that constitutes biometric data, while analysis of eye movements and individual choices can infer sensitive data such as ethnic origin, religious or political opinion and sexual orientation. Moreover, it is even plausible to infer health data from movement and speech patterns that XR applications can analyse.

Since a standard XR device can possibly gather special categories of personal data by default, it is very likely that the compliance of the GDPR requirements to process such data are not met. The typical agreement to terms and conditions that digital platforms request, is not a valid consent vis a vis special categories of personal data. Non-intend of gathering such data is not accepted as an alternative to explicit consent. Moreover, the recent ruling of the CJEU confirmed that the disclosure of personal data, even if done according to the national legislation, but has the potential to indirectly give away a special category of personal data, should follow the GDPR provisions for special categories of personal data.⁵⁷ This ruling makes the case for potential processing of special categories of personal data by XR devices, even stronger. User awareness for the device's data gathering possibilities is desirable, particularly for XR applications aiming at individual assessment (e.g. working environment or education). A GDPR recital clarifying the issue of XR devices is urgently needed.

For XR software that is integrated with AI, the AI Act makes specific references to biometric and sensitive data while attempting to regulate their use. A particular case is made for remote biometric identification (e.g. facial recognition) that is considered high-risk and is only allowed under strict conditions, including risk assessments, transparency obligations and human oversight. Similarly, processing sensitive data (e.g. health data, ethnic origin, political opinions, etc.) is considered high-risk especially if used in law enforcement, in employment or in access to essential services. As with GDPR, XR applications must declare intention to accumulate and process such data in their AI-based systems and subsequently follow the AI Act stipulations.

An important challenge in this regard is the existence of biometric data that falls out of the scope of the GDPR. Article 4(14) GDPR defines biometric data as physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics that *allows* the unique identification of an individual, and thus constitutes personal data. This kind of data is known as "hard" biometric data by the literature.⁵⁷ However, there are biometrics that do not allow for the identification of a person, which is known as "soft" biometric data. Soft biometrics has been defined as "*characteristics that provide some information about the individual, but lack the distinctiveness and permanence to sufficiently differentiate any two individuals*".⁵⁸ Examples of soft biometric data are hair colour, height, gait, keystroke and voice.⁵⁹ Soft biometric data is not regulated by the GDPR (or the AI Act),⁶⁰ and that lack of applicable regulation may represent an important affection to the privacy rights of the XR users.

A particularly grey area for XR, as discussed above, is the prohibited AI practices that include AI systems that use subliminal techniques to manipulate individuals or exploit vulnerabilities. The potential for self-

⁵⁷ EL Leijten and AR Lodder, 'On AI That Knows How We Feel, Without Knowing Who We Are: EU Law and the Processing of Soft Biometric Data by Emotional AI' in R Ballardini, R van den Hoven van Genderen and S Järvinen (eds), *Emotional Data Applications and Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in Society* (Law, Governance and Technology Series, vol 69, Springer 2025) 102.

⁵⁸ AK Jain, SC Dass and K Nandakumar, 'Soft Biometric Traits for Personal Recognition Systems' in D Zhang and AK Jain (eds), *Biometric Authentication. ICBA 2004* (Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 3072, Springer 2004) 732.

⁵⁹ European Commission, 'Soft Biometrics and Data Labelling for Privacy Preservation' (CORDIS, 2024) <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/soft-biometrics-and-data-labelling-for-privacy-preservation> Accessed 28 August 2025.

⁶⁰ n(52), 102 – 104.

immersion and heightened surveillance that XR applications have can result, in principle, in a dangerous combination of processing sensitive data while promoting manipulation. It would therefore be vital to have additional clarity in terms of the effects of the AI Act in this respect.

2.3. Invasive uses in the workplace and education

Workplace and education are two specific areas where personal data processing can result in wide-reaching impact on individual wellbeing. At the same time, these are areas that can benefit significantly from big data processing in terms of effective businesses and beneficial planning. XR applications have concentrated in both areas, either as tools of training or as tools of learning, with considerable success. There are nevertheless regulatory implications in XR use that must be taken into consideration. The more penetrating the application in the individual sphere, the more difficult (and important) regulatory compliance is. The two main regulations in this respect are the GDPR and the AI Act.

Under GDPR, personal data gathered in the workplace or in educational settings is considered sensitive if it falls into one of the special categories listed in Article 9 (e.g., health data, biometric data, or data revealing racial or ethnic origin). Processing such data is subject to stricter conditions and requires a valid legal basis while organisations must ensure compliance with the requirements for sensitive data, including transparency, security, and accountability. Since XR applications can gather by default sensitive personal data (whether or not intentionally, as we have seen above), organisations must conduct specific data protection impact assessments (DPIAs) before the deployment of XR in these fields.

For personal data gathered in the workplace, employees are given specific rights under GDPR, such as the right to access their personal data, the right to rectify inaccurate data, the right to erasure, and importantly, the right to object to processing. Considering that the obligation to free informed consent is also a cornerstone for gathering and processing data, it is doubtful that workplace monitoring can take place under the standard GDPR provisions. This leaves many XR applications in legal uncertainty⁶¹.

Moreover, GDPR (Article 22) also addresses automated decision making (including decisions made by AI systems) in the workplace and educational settings. These can be decisions on hiring, terminating a contract, or promoting an individual in the workplace, and admitting, grading, or assessing performance of a student in the educational setting. In both cases, individuals have the right to be informed about the logic behind such decisions and opt out of any automated decision making. They can also legally challenge any decision based on automation. This also creates uncertainty about the legality of the deployment of AI systems in XR applications in the workplace and educational setting.

The AI Act is quite specific on applications in the workplace or in education. The Act prohibits AI systems to infer emotions of a natural person in the areas of workplace and education institutions, except where the use of the system is intended for medical or safety reasons. Emotion recognition systems that do not fall under the prohibition are considered high-risk. It's important to note that the AI Act interprets the term "workplace" very broadly. It relates to any specific physical or virtual space where natural persons engage in tasks and responsibilities assigned by their employer or by the organisation they are affiliated

⁶¹ Legal uncertainty here involves the intentional or unintentional gathering of personal data whether by directly by the employer or entities operating on their behalf (e.g. the device manufacturer or the owner of the XR application).

to. It also applies to the selection and hiring process. That means that any XR application in the field using AI systems, must be fully aware of the prohibitive AI practices.

As we have seen, prohibited AI systems are also those that manipulate human behaviour or exploit vulnerabilities. This could apply to workplace monitoring systems that result in undue pressure or manipulate (directly or indirectly) employees. At the same time high risk AI systems are those that are used in employment decision-making (e.g. recruitment, performance evaluation, promotion, or termination), or in the educational setting, systems that determine access or outcomes (e.g., grading, admission, or personalized learning). This approach potentially makes any XR application in these fields high risk, so long as it employs an AI system.

With the exponential use of AI in every aspect of technological development, it is hard to imagine an XR system that will not involve AI in the future. Since the penalties for non-compliance with the AI Act can result in significant fines (up to 6% of global annual turnover for companies), organizations using AI in the workplace or education must ensure their systems comply with the Act's requirements, particularly for high-risk applications. For this reason, it is of outmost importance to get a clarity in the AI Act as to what exactly constitutes a prohibited or high-risk system in relation to XR applications in entertainment, workplace and education.

2.4. Bystanders' personal data collection

XR devices have the potential to capture personal data not only from the users, but from people that are around them – bystanders. This may seem nothing new, as other technologies, like CCTV, smart home and smartphones' cameras, already capture personal data from bystanders in public and private spaces. But what makes it different is that data processing by XR devices (especially AR) is defined by its subtleness and ease of recording.⁶² That represents an important challenge in regards compliance with the data protection framework.

None of the existing EU regulations in the data protection framework explicitly use the term "bystander". However, it seems clear that bystanders are themselves "data subjects" under the GDPR. The term "third party" in the GDPR⁶³ refers to a person who, under the direct authority of the controller or processor, is authorised to process personal data, not to the person whose data is actually being processed, thus not applicable to bystanders.

The main challenge is that there is a situation of power unbalance between the user of the XR device and the bystander,⁶⁴ when it comes to acknowledge their data is being captured, the lawfulness of such processing, and the possibility to exercise their data subject rights under the GDPR. The GDPR requires an informed consent for personal data processing (if another legal basis not applicable) or explicit consent when it comes to biometric data, which is captured by XR hardware.⁶⁵ Such consent is impractical to obtain in most cases (i.e. public or shared XR spaces). Although some XR providers have implemented technical measures directed to protect bystanders privacy (e.g. having a built-in LED light

⁶² M McAtamney, T Koskela and N Oulasvirta, 'In Situ with Bystanders of Augmented Reality Glasses' in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (ACM Press 2013)

⁶³ Article 4(10), GDPR

⁶⁴ Zeng, E Van Velsen and H Hermens, 'Privacy Concerns of Bystanders in Smart Homes' (2017) 15 *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 58.

⁶⁵ Please refer to Section 2.2. above.

in AR devices that lets bystanders know when the user is recording the content or going live)⁶⁶, they would not suffice GDPR's consent requirements.

The GDPR, however, gives an exemption when it comes to private spaces – it “does not apply to the processing of personal data by a natural person in the course of a purely personal or household activity”.⁶⁷ This only relates to the XR user, though, but not to the XR provider, as GDPR still “applies to controllers or processors which provide the means for processing personal data for such personal or household activities”.⁶⁸ In summary, even in the case of domestic use of XR devices, the XR provider must comply with the GDPR provisions.

⁶⁶ Takhshid, 'Wearable AI, Bystander Notice, and the Question of Privacy Frictions' (2024) 104(4) *Boston University Law Review* 1087.

⁶⁷ Recital 18, GDPR. This would be the case of e.g. recording a personal video during holidays whereby a lot of bystanders are also captured in it.

⁶⁸ Recital 18, GDPR.

3. Psychosocial challenges

3.1. Inauthentic identities and deepfakes

As XR technologies continue to evolve, they introduce new risks associated with inauthentic identities and deepfakes, reshaping digital interactions across various sectors. Deepfake technology, driven by AI-generated facial, voice, and behavioural replication, has reached a level of realism that challenges traditional regulatory safeguards. While certain EU regulations acknowledge digital identity manipulation as a risk, the regulatory framework remains fragmented, with no unified approach to addressing deepfake-related threats in immersive environments⁶⁹⁻⁷⁰⁻⁷¹.

The Convention on Cybercrime (Budapest Convention) criminalizes computer-related forgery and fraud, including digital identity falsification⁷². However, its scope is limited to conventional online deception rather than the dynamic and immersive nature of deepfake fraud in XR environments.

The AVMSD and the DSA impose obligations on online platforms to moderate content, yet these regulations primarily focus on traditional video and social media rather than real-time manipulation of identity within virtual spaces⁷³. Meanwhile, the GDPR offers individuals control over their personal data, including biometric information, yet does not explicitly regulate AI-generated deepfakes creating entirely synthetic identities – a critical loophole in protection against identity fraud⁷⁴.

Despite attempts to improve data transparency under the DGA and the Data Act, no explicit measures exist to prevent AI-driven identity fraud or regulate the datasets used for deepfake training⁷⁵. Similarly, while the TSD protects proprietary business information, it does not address unauthorised replication of executives or employees via deepfake technology, leaving businesses vulnerable to commercial identity fraud. The AI Act acknowledges the risks of manipulative AI-generated content but primarily emphasizes transparency rather than enforcing strict preventative measures⁷⁶. Furthermore, specific regulations such as the GPSR do not currently account for hardware-enabled identity fraud, such as biometric spoofing through facial replication technologies.

The current EU regulatory framework lacks a cohesive and forward-looking approach to mitigating deepfake-driven identity fraud dangers, particularly in XR environments where AI-generated representations may seamlessly mimic real individuals. Existing directives and regulations address fragmented aspects of digital identity security yet fail to comprehensively regulate synthetic identities, particularly in immersive, real-time interactions⁷⁷.

⁶⁹ European Parliament, *Virtual Worlds – Opportunities, Risks and Policy Implications for the Single Market* (Study, Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, 2024) paras 14, 19 and 22.

⁷⁰ European Parliament, *Policy Implications of the Development of Virtual Worlds – Civil, Company, Commercial and Intellectual Property Law Issues* (Study, Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs, 2024) para 29

⁷¹ European Parliamentary Research Service, *Children and Deepfakes* (European Parliament, 2025) 3–5 https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI%282025%29775855 accessed 25 August 2025

⁷² Council of Europe, Budapest Convention, Articles 7 and 8.

⁷³ Article 7, AVMSD; Article 17, DSA.

⁷⁴ Articles 4(14) and 9(1), GDPR; n(64) para. 29.

⁷⁵ Europol Innovation Lab, *Facing Reality? Law Enforcement and the Challenge of Deepfakes* (Europol 2022) 7.

⁷⁶ Recital 142, AI Act

⁷⁷ European Commission, *An EU Initiative on Web 4.0 and Virtual Worlds: A Head Start in the Next Technological Transition* COM(2023) 442 final p. 5.

One major gap is the absence of explicit provisions on deepfake detection and authentication in data protection and cybersecurity regulations. Protections to biometric data under the GDPR apply only when derived from real individuals, meaning AI-generated synthetic faces, voices, and avatars may fall outside existing privacy laws if the real person is not at least identifiable, creating significant loopholes allowing impersonation without explicit legal consequences. Similarly, the AI Act mandates transparency in AI-generated content yet lacks specific enforcement mechanisms to prevent deepfake avatar misuse in fraud, misinformation, or identity theft⁷⁸.

Another critical gap lies in insufficient liability frameworks for AI-generated impersonations in business and financial transactions. The TSD does not currently consider synthetic identity fraud as a corporate risk, leaving businesses exposed to reputational damage and fraudulent transactions carried out under deepfake-generated pretences. Additionally, the AMLD⁷⁹ do not mandate specific fraud detection measures against AI-driven financial impersonation, such as deepfakes in banking and crypto-asset transactions.

The DSA and AVMSD attempt to regulate deceptive digital content but fall short in addressing real-time manipulation of identity in XR and live deepfake-generated interactions. Current moderation obligations for online platforms focus on pre-recorded content, failing to account for live-streamed or dynamically generated deepfake avatars used for fraud, misinformation, or harassment⁸⁰. Likewise, the Convention on Cybercrime, while criminalising digital forgery, does not specifically define the use of AI-generated deepfakes for identity fraud as a high-risk offence, leaving a legal grey area regarding deepfake-enabled scams and identity theft⁸¹.

3.2. Addiction, isolation and other psychosocial risks

Psychosocial risks such as addiction, isolation, cognitive overload, anxiety, and depression are partially recognized in EU law, though often indirectly and without explicit reference to XR. While some laws acknowledge digital risks and consumer vulnerabilities, none comprehensively address the unique immersive and interactive nature of XR environments.

The GPSR includes mental health risks as part of its safety assessment obligations for digital products, particularly concerning vulnerable users such as children⁸². Similarly, the UCPD highlights the susceptibility of vulnerable consumers to manipulative business practices, including those that exploit psychological vulnerabilities⁸³.

The AI Act indirectly addresses some psychosocial risks by prohibiting AI applications that exploit vulnerabilities due to age or disability⁸⁴. This applies to AI-driven XR applications that manipulate user behaviour or decision-making, particularly among children or individuals with mental health challenges. However, the AI Act does not currently classify addictive, anxiety-inducing or psychologically immersive XR experiences as high-risk.

⁷⁸ Article 95(e), AI Act.

⁷⁹ Article 13(1), AMLD and Article 8, EMD

⁸⁰ Article 7, AVMSD; Article 17, DSA.

⁸¹ Articles 7 and 8 Budapest Convention

⁸² n(2) Section 5.3; Recital 23, GPSR

⁸³ n(2) Section 5.4; Article 5(3), UCPD

⁸⁴ See n(2), S 9.

The DSA mandates risk assessments for very large online platforms (VLOPs), including measures to protect minors from harmful content⁸⁵. Yet, its applicability to XR remains unclear, as most XR platforms do not meet the user threshold to be classified as VLOPs⁸⁶. Moreover, while the AVMSD regulates harmful media content that promotes discrimination based on demographic distinguishers⁸⁷, addictive substances⁸⁸, and content pertaining to the vulnerability of minors⁸⁹, its provisions primarily focus on traditional audiovisual formats⁹⁰, leaving immersive and interactive XR experiences outside its direct scope.

The first and foremost crucial gap lies in the absence of explicit recognition of XR-induced psychosocial risks. While the GPSR acknowledges mental health risks, it does not specify how immersive digital environments contribute to addiction, isolation, or identity confusion. This lack of XR-specific guidance leaves manufacturers and developers without clear obligations to assess and mitigate these risks during product design.

Second, there is an insufficient protection against manipulative design, for instance, The UCPD – that prohibits practices that exploit consumers' vulnerabilities – does not address the immersive and persuasive nature of XR environments. XR applications can integrate AI-driven behavioural tracking and dynamic reward systems that foster addiction, yet no regulation explicitly restricts such manipulative design practices.

The third major gap lies in the applicability of risk assessment requirements. For instance, the DSA applies risk assessments only to VLOPs, excluding the majority of XR platforms that fall below the user threshold. This creates a significant regulatory gap, as smaller XR platforms may still expose users to harmful immersive experiences without being subject to the DSA's risk mitigation requirements.

Fourth, there are gaps in content moderation, especially with respect to psychosocial harm. The AVMSD mandates content moderation for harmful media but primarily targets traditional audiovisual formats.

Lastly, there is also an absence of usage limitations or time-based warnings. No regulation—neither the GPSR, UCPD, nor DSA—currently mandates usage limitations, time-based warnings, or built-in tools to manage screen time in XR applications leaving a potential for psychosocial impacts such as addiction due to prolonged exposure.

3.3. Harmful behaviour, offensive and violent interactions

As XR technologies continue to expand, they bring new dimensions to online interactions, including heightened risks of harmful behaviour, offensive content, and violent interactions. XR's immersive nature amplifies the psychological and emotional impact of online abuse, making harassment, cyberbullying, and other forms of violence significantly more severe than in traditional digital spaces. While several EU regulations provide partial protections against these risks, the current legal framework remains fragmented, lacking cohesive and XR-specific safeguards⁹¹.

⁸⁵ Article 34, DSA

⁸⁶ See n(2), S 6.2.

⁸⁷ Article 9(1)(c), AVMSD

⁸⁸ Article 9(1)(d), AVMSD

⁸⁹ Article 28b(1)(a), AVMSD

⁹⁰ See n(2), S 6.1.

⁹¹ n(63) para. 14, 19 and 22.

The DSA is one of the most relevant EU regulations addressing harmful content and behaviour online. It establishes obligations for online platforms to moderate illegal content, combat disinformation, and protect users, particularly minors⁹². However, many XR platforms do not yet meet the threshold for VLOPs, which means they are not subject to the DSA's most stringent requirements, leaving many immersive environments under-regulated⁹³. This has been further elaborated in Section 4.5 of this Report. Additionally, the AVMSD imposes obligations on video-sharing platforms to prevent incitement to violence and protect minors from harmful content, but it does not explicitly extend to interactive and immersive XR spaces⁹⁴.

The Convention on Cybercrime criminalises cyber-harassment, stalking, and hate speech, but its enforcement depends on national laws, leading to inconsistent application across Member States⁹⁵. The NIS2 Directive, addressing cybersecurity threats, includes measures to protect users from cyber manipulation and virtual identity theft but does not directly tackle offensive behaviour within XR social interactions⁹⁶. Furthermore, the CSAR provides essential safeguards against exploitation and grooming in digital spaces, yet its scope remains focused primarily on child protection rather than broader violent and offensive interactions in XR⁹⁷.

A pressing concern is that XR-specific attacks and manipulative behaviours – such as man-in-the-room attacks, human joystick attacks, and disorientation attacks – are not explicitly covered under existing regulations. These forms of abuse can have severe psychological and physical consequences, yet no binding EU laws mandate XR service providers to protect users from these threats⁹⁸.

Despite multiple EU regulations aimed at online safety, significant gaps remain in addressing harmful behaviour, offensive content, and violent interactions in XR environments. These gaps can be grouped into three critical areas: (a) lack of comprehensive moderation obligations, (b) inadequate risk classification, and (c) weak enforcement mechanisms for immersive digital environments⁹⁹.

(a) Lack of comprehensive moderation obligations in XR platforms: The DSA and AVMSD regulate content moderation on social media and video-sharing platforms, but XR spaces are not explicitly recognised as high-risk environments under these laws. This loophole allows harmful interactions on XR social platforms (e.g., VRChat, Horizon Worlds, Rec Room) to proliferate with limited regulatory oversight. Unlike traditional social media, XR interactions feel more real due to presence, immersion, and embodiment effects, making verbal abuse, harassment, and violent content far more impactful on users¹⁰⁰.

(b) Inadequate risk classification of XR-related harms: EU law inadequately classify immersive digital harms. While the AI Act recognises manipulative AI systems as high-risk, it does not explicitly regulate the use of AI-powered avatars, voice cloning, or behavioural profiling, leaving users vulnerable to psychological manipulation, predatory monetisation, and emotional coercion that may be more effective in XR interactions¹⁰¹. Additionally, cybersecurity protections under the NIS2 Directive address data

⁹² Article 17, DSA.

⁹³ See n(2).

⁹⁴ Article 7 AVMSD; For a detailed understanding, see n(2), S 6.1.

⁹⁵ Articles 7, 8, and 10, Council of Europe, Budapest Convention; also see n(2).

⁹⁶ Article 21, Directive (EU) 2022/2555; Also see n(2).

⁹⁷ European Commission, Proposal for a Regulation laying down rules to prevent and combat child sexual abuse, COM(2022) 209 final; also see n(2).

⁹⁸ See n(2).

⁹⁹ n(71) p. 5.

¹⁰⁰ n(64), para. 29.

¹⁰¹ Article 95(e), AI Act; also see n(2).

breaches and hacking risks but overlook social XR attacks such as man-in-the-room intrusions or human joystick attacks, physically manipulating users in immersive spaces¹⁰².

(c) Weak enforcement mechanisms for immersive digital environments: Even where EU laws apply, enforcement remains limited. The AVMSD obliges platforms to prevent incitement to violence but lacks strong enforcement provisions for real-time XR interactions, where harmful behaviour occurs instantaneously and is challenging to moderate¹⁰³. Similarly, the DSA establishes transparency obligations for digital platforms, but many XR platforms currently fall outside the scope of these obligations due to smaller user bases¹⁰⁴. Additionally, age verification mechanisms to protect minors in XR spaces remain weak, leaving children vulnerable to harassment, exposure to violent content, and online grooming¹⁰⁵.

3.4. User targeting and emotional manipulation

The DSA prohibits deceptive design practices, such as ‘dark patterns’, where online platforms manipulate users into making decisions not aligned with their best interests¹⁰⁶. However, this prohibition is limited to the design of online interfaces and does not explicitly cover real-time behavioural manipulation in immersive digital environments¹⁰⁷. UCPD addresses deceptive marketing and aggressive sales tactics, ensuring consumers are not misled or coerced into purchases¹⁰⁸. However, the UCPD’s traditional consumer protection framework does not fully account for the psychological intensity of immersive advertising in XR, where users may experience hyper-personalised persuasion through AI-driven interactions¹⁰⁹.

The GDPR sets strict limits on user profiling and targeted advertising, particularly regarding sensitive personal data such as biometric tracking, increasingly used in XR advertising to measure user reactions and adjust content accordingly¹¹⁰. However, GDPR enforcement is often slow and reactive, allowing manipulative practices to proliferate before regulatory intervention occurs. The DMA places obligations on large online platforms (‘gatekeepers’) to ensure fair competition but does not specifically regulate biometric and emotional data usage for targeted advertising in XR¹¹¹.

Additionally, the AVMSD applies some advertising restrictions to XR, particularly where AR and VR elements are integrated into digital marketing strategies. However, this regulation primarily focuses on traditional audiovisual content, leaving immersive and interactive XR advertising largely unregulated¹¹². Furthermore, the DGA and DA establish rules for data sharing and transparency but do not explicitly address ethical concerns surrounding behavioural targeting in XR.

While current EU regulations attempt to address consumer protection and data privacy, they fail to fully capture the unique risks posed by XR advertising and behavioural manipulation. The three primary

¹⁰² Article 21, Directive (EU) 2022/2555; also see n (2).

¹⁰³ Article 7, AVMSD; also see n (2).

¹⁰⁴ Article 17, DSA; also see n (2).

¹⁰⁵ For a detailed understanding, also see n (2).

¹⁰⁶ Article 25, DSA.

¹⁰⁷ n (63), para. 14, 19 and 22.

¹⁰⁸ Article 5, UCPD

¹⁰⁹ n (64), para. 29.

¹¹⁰ Articles 4(14) and 9(1), GDPR.

¹¹¹ Article 5, DMA

¹¹² Article 9, AVMSD.

regulatory gaps in this area are (a) inadequate safeguards against biometric and emotional data exploitation, (b) lack of enforcement mechanisms for immersive and manipulative advertising, and (c) insufficient transparency obligations for AI-driven persuasion techniques¹¹³

(a) Inadequate safeguards against soft biometric and emotion data exploitation: Current EU laws, such as GDPR, protect personal data from misuse but do not specifically regulate soft biometric data,¹¹⁴ Therefore, they are out of the scope of the GDPR. Another type of personal data that lacks proper protection is emotion data, which is defined in the literature as “*information about a person’s inner emotional state, such as their subjective response to a thing, person, or situation*”, including anger, disgust, fear, happiness, sadness, and surprise. Despite its intimate nature and having an important potential of being misused for manipulation, emotion data is not considered as personal data when the individual cannot be identified nor identifiable, and when it is personal data, is not considered a special category of data under Article 9 GDPR. Both types of data may be collected by XR providers for personalised advertising and real-time user engagement. The lack of a proper protection by the GDPR enables companies to exploit subconscious reactions and shape consumer behaviour.¹¹⁵

(b) Lack of enforcement mechanisms for immersive and manipulative advertising: The DSA prohibits dark patterns, yet this ban does not extend explicitly to immersive XR environments, where persuasive design and subliminal messaging are seamlessly integrated into user experiences¹¹⁶. Unlike traditional pop-up ads or misleading button placements, XR advertising may be deeply embedded into virtual spaces, making it harder to detect and regulate. Additionally, the UCPD’s restrictions on aggressive marketing do not account for AI-powered avatars that can emotionally manipulate users into making purchasing decisions¹¹⁷.

(c) Insufficient transparency obligations for AI-driven persuasion techniques: While the AI Act recognises risks associated with AI-driven decision-making, it does not impose specific transparency requirements on platforms (XR or otherwise) using AI-generated avatars, recommendation systems, or behavioural nudging to influence users¹¹⁸. Additionally, there are no clear disclosure requirements for companies using emotional AI in advertising, leaving consumers unaware of how their subconscious responses are monitored and exploited¹¹⁹.

3.5. Children and other vulnerable users

XR technologies pose significant psychosocial risks to children and other vulnerable users due to their immersive nature¹²⁰, which can intensify experiences of harassment, manipulation, and exposure to harmful content. The heightened realism of XR environments increases the likelihood of psychosocial harm, making users more susceptible to issues such as cybercrime, exploitation, and identity-based discrimination. However, most existing EU regulations are concerned with data protection and handling

¹¹³ n (71), p. 5.

¹¹⁴ Please refer to Section 2.2 above.

¹¹⁵ Andreas Hauselmann, Alan M. Sears, Lex Zard and Eduard Fosch-Villaronga, ‘EU law and emotion data’ in *arXiv (Cornell University)*(2023) <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2309.10776> Accessed 28 August 2025.

¹¹⁶ Article 25, DSA.

¹¹⁷ Article 5, UCPD

¹¹⁸ Article 95(e), AI Act.

¹¹⁹ n (63), para. 14, 19 and 22.

¹²⁰ XR4Human, Policy Report, pp. 38-39

of data of such users (such as the GDPR, the ePrivacy Directive, the Data Act, and the DGA), and offer only partial and often unclear protections against these psychosocial risks.

Several EU regulations explicitly recognize children and other vulnerable users, such as persons with disabilities and individuals susceptible to exploitation. While the GDPR focuses on adding extra protection to the processing of special categories of personal data such as race, health data or political opinion that render them vulnerable to their rights and freedoms¹²¹ and sets special requirements for the processing of children's data, the UCPD has a more comprehensive approach by acknowledging vulnerable consumers and emphasizing the need to assess commercial practices from the perspective of those who may be disproportionately affected due to age, mental or physical infirmity, or credulity¹²². The AVMSD mandates protections against harmful content, particularly for minors, and prohibits advertisements that could negatively impact their well-being¹²³. The GPSR includes obligations to assess mental health risks associated with digital and interconnected devices, particularly for children¹²⁴. The EAA and the WAD ensure that digital services, including XR applications, remain accessible to individuals with disabilities¹²⁵.

Certain regulations acknowledge the psychological and social risks posed by digital environments, that are therefore applicable to XR. The DSA highlights the need for proportionate measures to protect minors' safety and privacy online¹²⁶, though its application to XR will be reduced or softened due to its user-based categorization of platforms¹²⁷. The AI Act classifies AI systems that exploit children's vulnerabilities as "unacceptable risk," warranting outright prohibition¹²⁸. The CSAR specifically addresses online child exploitation risks, imposing obligations on platforms, including those using XR, to mitigate such dangers¹²⁹. Additionally, the Convention on Cybercrime recognizes child pornography as a cybercrime and mandates risk assessments and relevant mitigation measures¹³⁰, but lacks provisions addressing novel XR-specific threats, such as virtual sexual assaults¹³¹.

In the context of XR, these regulations provide a fragmented but evolving framework for addressing psychosocial risks. While laws like the CSAR, GPSR, and AVMSD impose obligations on XR platforms and hardware to protect users from harmful content, others, such as the UCPD and DSA, highlight concerns over manipulative commercial practices and surveillance in immersive environments. However, enforcement mechanisms and oversight remain inconsistent, particularly regarding age verification, content moderation, and psychological harm mitigation in XR spaces. Strengthening regulatory clarity and enforcement is crucial to effectively safeguarding children and vulnerable users in immersive digital environments.

A significant gap exists due to the lack of clear protections against psychological harm, particularly to vulnerable users of XR. While the GPSR requires risk assessments for mental health impacts, it only provides a broad directive to mitigate of these risks. The Medical Devices Regulation (MDR) also

¹²¹ See n(2), S 3.1.

¹²² See n(2), S 5.4.

¹²³ See n(2), S 6.1; Article 28b(1)(a), AVMSD.

¹²⁴ See n(2), S 5.3; Recital 23, GPSR

¹²⁵ See n(2), S 8.1 and 8.2.

¹²⁶ Article 21, DSA

¹²⁷ See n(2), S 6.2.

¹²⁸ See n(2), S 9; Recital 31, AI Act

¹²⁹ See n(2), S 7.3.

¹³⁰ Articles 3(1) and 4(3), CSAR

¹³¹ See n(2), S 7.1.

mandates risk assessments for medical applications of XR technologies¹³², however, there is no clear mandate for assessing psychosocial risks and mitigating them.

Another critical gap lies in the insufficient content moderation and child protection mechanisms. The AVMSD and the DSA contain provisions for protecting minors from harmful content, but these regulations primarily focus on traditional media and social platforms. XR environments present unique challenges, such as real-time interactions, spatial audio, and avatar-based anonymity, which complicate content moderation. Furthermore, the CSAR mandates risk assessments and mitigation measures for child exploitation, yet enforcement mechanisms in XR remain unclear, particularly regarding virtual harassment and grooming.

Similarly, weak age verification and safety controls continue to be a challenge. While the CSAR requires age verification measures for platforms hosting child-directed content, current implementations remain ineffective, where users can create multiple avatars and bypass traditional verification methods. Similarly, the DSA mandates protection for minors but lacks specific guidelines for enforcing age restrictions and parental controls in XR applications.

Also, in commercial applications, there is a gap due to the limited oversight of manipulative commercial practices. The UCPD recognizes the vulnerability of children and certain users to deceptive marketing but does not explicitly regulate advertising techniques potentially implemented in XR, such as real-time behavioural tracking and AI-driven persuasion tactics. The DGA and the Data Act promote fair data sharing but do not restrict the collection of biometric and behavioural data from XR users, leaving children particularly vulnerable to profiling and targeted advertising.

Additionally, certain accessibility gaps exist for vulnerable users. The EAA and WAD mandate accessibility for digital services, but their applicability to XR remains vague. XR interactions rely heavily on visual and motion-based controls, which can create barriers for individuals with disabilities. The lack of standardized accessibility requirements for XR devices and applications results in inconsistent implementation across the industry.

Lastly, certain enforcement and regulatory overlap issues also exist. Many regulations, including the DSA, CSAR, and AVMSD, impose obligations on digital service providers but do not provide clear enforcement mechanisms for XR environments. Additionally, the Convention on Cybercrime criminalizes child pornography but does not address emerging XR-specific crimes such as virtual sexual assaults or adult impersonation of children. This regulatory uncertainty creates challenges in holding XR platform providers accountable for user safety.

Overall, while existing EU regulations provide a fragmented framework for addressing psychosocial risks, they fail to comprehensively account for the immersive, real-time, and interactive nature of XR technology. Without clear guidance on enforcement, risk assessment, and protective measures, children and other vulnerable users remain exposed to significant psychosocial threats in XR environments.

¹³² See n (2), S 10.1.

4. Economic and societal challenges

4.1. Digital literacy, access and affordability

In our previous work, we have identified that digital literacy¹³³, access and affordability¹³⁴ are policy challenges for the XR environment. These may be financial or societal barriers to the adoption of XR technologies for vulnerable persons, like elderly population, people with disabilities, and lower-middle-income population, among others. These three concepts have been set as policy goals that the EP has set in its Resolution on Virtual Worlds.¹³⁵ However, their transformation into legal obligations is uneven – while accessibility can be found in several regulations of general and specific application to XR companies, affordability and literacy mostly remain as policy goals or are legally implemented in exceptional cases for the XR ecosystem, as highlighted below.

Literacy is included in provisions that govern some specific XR products and services. For example, the AVMSD addresses media literacy, which refers to "*skills, knowledge and understanding that allow consumers to use media effectively and safely*".¹³⁶ Under the AVMSD, Member States must ensure companies offering XR-based streaming platforms to provide "*for effective media literacy measures and tools and raising users' awareness of those measures and tools*".¹³⁷ In addition, XR providers that qualify as providers or deployers of AI systems under the AI Act, would be obliged to adopt literacy efforts for their employees that produce and use AI.¹³⁸ However, these obligations are very specific and do not apply to all XR providers, so there is an important gap when it comes to digital literacy for the XR ecosystem. Ultimately, when applied to XR providers, these norms do not refer to knowledge of or awareness of XR technology. For these reasons, the EP has stressed the need of broad (XR) literacy for citizens through a 'virtual worlds toolbox'.¹³⁹

In contrast, the principle of accessibility is supported by a strong legal framework that generally applies to XR providers, which includes the EAA and the WAD.¹⁴⁰ Under the EAA, manufacturers of XR hardware need to ensure that products meet accessibility requirements when placed on the market, through the conduction of conformity assessments and 'CE' marking.¹⁴¹ On the software side, the WAD targets mobile applications in the XR environment to meet accessibility standards, making content perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust.¹⁴² The obligations under the EAA and the WAD are reinforced by the voluntary codes of conduct of the DSA, aimed to "*promote full and effective, equal participation, by improving access to online services that, through their initial design or subsequent adaptation, address the particular needs of persons with disabilities*".¹⁴³

In addition to the general framework, there are accessibility obligations for specific XR providers. For those XR companies that qualify as media services providers under the AVMSD, they need to "*ensure that*

¹³³ See n (1), S 5.2.1.

¹³⁴ See n (1), S 9.2 and XR4Human, D2.2 S 3.2.5.2.

¹³⁵ n (63), para 29; n (64), para. 29.

¹³⁶ Recital 47, AVMSD.

¹³⁷ Article 28b(3)(j), AVMSD.

¹³⁸ Article 25, AI Act.

¹³⁹ n (64), para. 31-32.

¹⁴⁰ European Commission, *An EU Initiative on Web 4.0 and Virtual Worlds: A Head Start in the Next Technological Transition* COM(2023) 442 final, 5.

¹⁴¹ See n (2), S 8.1.

¹⁴² See n (2), S 8.2

¹⁴³ Article 47, DSA.

their services are gradually made accessible to people with a visual or hearing disability".¹⁴⁴ The AI Act acknowledges the importance of the accessibility framework when using AI systems, and establishes obligations in this regard, although these are directed to providers of such systems,¹⁴⁵ rather than deployers, which is most likely the category that could apply to XR companies. However, providers and deployers of AI systems that voluntarily adopt codes of conduct will also be bounded by accessibility requirements.¹⁴⁶ Member States are also encouraged to "support and promote research and development of [...] AI-based solutions to increase accessibility for persons with disabilities"¹⁴⁷.

Lastly, the regulations analysed by our previous work do not contain any affordability obligations related to XR hardware, and it seems unlikely that this will change in the foreseeable future, considering the political context and the priorities of the European Commission regarding new technologies. As such, it will probably remain as a generic policy goal for EU institutions and Member States rather than an obligation for XR companies.

Overall, there is a regulatory gap with regard to XR literacy and affordability, that could be resolved in the form of guidelines in the DSA's voluntary codes of conduct, as this regulation is generally applicable to XR platform providers.

4.2. Ownership of digital assets and crypto assets

There are some challenges to the property of digital assets in XR environments.¹⁴⁸ We consider digital assets to be any digital representation of an object or person (e.g. digital art, in-game assets), even if does not have a non-digital counterpart.¹⁴⁹ Intellectual Property (IP) regulations apply to the ownership of digital assets.

Digital assets that exist in a virtual environment, including user-generated content (UGC), will be subject to the Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market. For the case of UGC, XR platforms are likely to follow the industry practices of incorporating mutual (copyright) licences in their terms of services, so users can make use of the digital assets and functions provided by the platform, while platforms can deploy such creations with the user's permission, as users are the authors and thus the copyright holders of the UGC.

Other IP regulations that may apply to digital assets are the Regulation on the EU Trademarks, when it comes to the use of registered trademarks, and the TSD, when trade secrets (e.g. know how) are displayed. Even though the relevance of IP law to the XR environment is not disputed,¹⁵⁰ both the literature and the EU institutions have acknowledged that there are some challenges to its applicability.

A first challenge is that some of the new forms of digital assets deployed in virtual worlds may not generate the ownership that users may expect to have. This is the case in the purchase of 'virtual real estate' (i.e. pieces of virtual land or buildings that are offered in the metaverse), which do not give origin

¹⁴⁴ Article 7, AVMSD.

¹⁴⁵ Articles 16(l) and 50(1), AI Act.

¹⁴⁶ Article 95(e), AI Act.

¹⁴⁷ Recital 142, AI Act.

¹⁴⁸ Please refer to our previous reports titled D3.1, S 7.2.3 and D2.2 S 3.2.5.3. <https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

¹⁴⁹ This is a broad concept of digital asset, in contrast with some restrictive definitions, like the one published by the European Law Institute in their [Principles on the Use of Digital Assets as Security](#) (p. 17).

¹⁵⁰ n(71) p. 5.

to traditional property rights under private law but eventually to a (copyright) license as previously explained.¹⁵¹ Another case are non-fungible tokens (NFTs), which do not grant any copyrights to the underlying content¹⁵² – in other words, the purchaser of an NFT will just have a (in some cases, licensed) copy of a copyrighted work, but there is no transfer of economic rights under the Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market. Nevertheless, the unmet expectations of ownership of digital assets could be deemed as a problem of lack of transparency and imbalance of information, rather than provoked by the (lack of) IP regulations.

A second challenge, as recognised by both the EP and the EC, is related to the enforcement of these IP regulations and identification of infringers in virtual environments.¹⁵³ Digital assets protected by copyright or trademarks can be easily reused in XR environments, with limited possibility for their titleholders to control such uses and enforce these IP regulations, especially when they are companies that do not participate in the XR ecosystem or do not have access to an specific XR platform when these infringements occur.¹⁵⁴ The DSA establishes general obligations that would help in the identification of IP infringements, including cooperation with national authorities following orders to act against illegal content,¹⁵⁵ establishing measures and protection against users providing manifestly illegal content,¹⁵⁶ and trusted flaggers of illegal content,¹⁵⁷ among others. Additionally, the EC has agreed to publish an IP toolbox to assist rights holders in enforcing their rights in the XR environment.¹⁵⁸

A specific category of digital assets that represent an additional problem is crypto-assets,¹⁵⁹ which are regulated by the MiCA.¹⁶⁰ A crypto-asset is "a digital representation of a value or of a right that is able to be transferred and stored electronically using distributed ledger technology or similar technology".¹⁶¹ There are three types of crypto assets: utility tokens, which grant access or rights (e.g. game tokens), financial tokens, when it is linked to an underlying asset (e.g. a firm, real estate or collectibles) and currency/payment tokens (e.g. Bitcoin).¹⁶² All these types of crypto-asset can be found on a number of XR platforms and, more broadly, in virtual worlds. The MiCA regulates the custody and administration of crypto-assets and their transaction. As previously mentioned in the case of NFTs, the difficulty in establishing ownership is derived from the technologic characteristics of crypto-assets, and it is not solved by the MiCA or any other current regulation. Therefore, it has been proposed that property rights in crypto-assets should be recognized under private law.¹⁶³ This would facilitate the implementation of crypto-assets on XR platforms, and enhance understanding and, ultimately, confidence in them among European users.

¹⁵¹ n (64), para. 18.

¹⁵² n (64), para. 26.

¹⁵³ n (63), para. 6; n (64), para. 22; n (71) p. 11.

¹⁵⁴ Please refer to our previous reports titled D3.1, S 7.2.3 and D2.2, S 3.2.5.3. <https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

¹⁵⁵ Articles 9-10, DSA

¹⁵⁶ Article 23, DSA.

¹⁵⁷ Article 22, DSA.

¹⁵⁸ n (71), p. 11

¹⁵⁹ Please refer to our previous report titled D2.2, S 3.2.5.2. <https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

¹⁶⁰ n (71), p. 5.

¹⁶¹ Article 3(5), MiCA

¹⁶² European Parliament, *Remaining Regulatory Challenges in Digital Finance and Crypto-Assets after MiCA* (Study, Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, 2023) 79–80.

¹⁶³ n (71), p. 51

4.3. Deceptive practices and unfair competition

Among the realm of challenges present in the XR environment, are malicious practices that companies providing XR products or services may incur, targeting and affecting both consumers and competitors and harming their economic interests.

A prime example, is the undermining of the rights of XR users through deceptive commercial practices that manipulate their economic behaviour, an effect that XR technologies may enhance due to their unique immersive nature.¹⁶⁴ Deceptive commercial practices have been widely addressed by the EU consumer law framework, particularly the UCPD,¹⁶⁵ as well as the GDPR, both generally applicable to providers of XR platforms. The UCPD forbids unfair commercial practices, which can be misleading (by action or omission), as well as aggressive,¹⁶⁶ and provides a list of commercial practices (known as the "UCPD blacklist") which details commercial practices which all in all circumstances considered unfair.¹⁶⁷ The GDPR also protects XR users from deceptive practices by establishing the principles of lawfulness, transparency, data minimisation and accountability.¹⁶⁸

Particularly, the EP has stated that one of such deceptive practices known as dark patterns must be especially addressed in virtual environments.¹⁶⁹ Dark patterns are "*interfaces and user journeys [...] that aim to influence users into making unintended, respectively unwilling, and/or potentially harmful decisions*"¹⁷⁰. According to the "Digital Fairness Fitness Check", some of the dark patterns are included in the UCPD blacklist, "*although none of [them] refer specifically to digital interfaces*",¹⁷¹ reason why Members States and stakeholders have requested additional guidance on dark patterns.¹⁷²

Another regulation that may be applicable in this regard is the DSA, which prohibits online providers – most XR services and applications fall into that category – to use interface design and organization that deceives or manipulates the recipients of their service,¹⁷³ targeting dark patterns like distortion of choices, nagging and difficult cancellations.¹⁷⁴ Such rules may be subject to guidelines by the EC,¹⁷⁵ which could use that opportunity to provide further advice for XR platforms.¹⁷⁶ Obligations for VLOPs under the DSA – including risk assessments,¹⁷⁷ mitigation measures,¹⁷⁸ and (mandatory) codes of conduct¹⁷⁹ – may also help to identify and reduce dark patterns. However, it is unlikely that any XR-focused platforms, will be designed as a VLOP in the near future.¹⁸⁰ This is one of a number of problems identified in the

¹⁶⁴ Please refer to our previous reports titled D2.2, S 3.2.3.4 and D3.2, S 5.4. <https://xr4human.eu/deliverables/>

¹⁶⁵ n (71), p. 5.

¹⁶⁶ Article 5, UCPD

¹⁶⁷ Annex I, UCPD

¹⁶⁸ Article 5(1)(a), (c) and (2), GDPR

¹⁶⁹ n (63), para. 18

¹⁷⁰ European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 03/2022 on Deceptive Design Patterns in Social Media Platform Interfaces: How to Recognise and Avoid Them* (2023) para 3

¹⁷¹ European Commission, *Fitness Check of EU Consumer Law on Digital Fairness* (2024) 148.

¹⁷² n (71), p. 59

¹⁷³ Article 25, DSA

¹⁷⁴ n (71), p. 150.

¹⁷⁵ Article 25(3), DSA

¹⁷⁶ Julian Jaurisch, *Opinion piece: The DSA also works "in the metaverse" – if it is enforced well* (Interface – Strengthening the Digital Public Sphere and Platform Regulation, Tagesspiegel Background Digitalisierung & KI, 14 December 2022), accessed 25 August 2025.

¹⁷⁷ Article 34, DSA.

¹⁷⁸ Article 35, DSA.

¹⁷⁹ Articles 45(1) and 48, DSA.

¹⁸⁰ See n (2) S 6.2.

implementation of the DSA on dark patterns – including the DSA's conflict and overlap with the UCPD –¹⁸¹ and the reason for the proposal of a new regulation targeting dark patterns broadly, to be known as the Digital Fairness Act.¹⁸²

In addition to these regulations, XR providers may also be subject to prohibitions on the use of dark patterns in specific cases, including for XR providers designated as gatekeepers under the DMA or those using AI systems under the AI Act.¹⁸³

Another challenge is that XR providers may engage in unfair competitive practices, including targeting competitors' products and services to damage their reputation, misrepresenting their own products and services under a third party's name or trademark, or using deceptive practices to promote their own products to users.¹⁸⁴ Several different rules may be applicable in this case. First, the fair competition framework, in particular Articles 101 and 102 of the TFEU, that generally apply to the XR environment.¹⁸⁵ Second, the TMR will be applicable in case of unauthorised use of a registered trademark owned by a competitor. Third, for the specific case of XR providers designated as gatekeepers under the DMA, competition is safeguarded by prohibitions of unfair practices like self-preference of their own products and services in rankings¹⁸⁶ and restriction to switch between different apps and services.¹⁸⁷ Finally, the aforementioned rules of the UCPD, although targeted to the protection of consumers, would also be indirectly beneficial to competitors.¹⁸⁸

4.4. Cybersecurity vulnerabilities

Cybersecurity threats in an XR environment include not only existing threats that occur in the online environment (data breaches, cybercrime, cyberterrorism, fraud, etc.),¹⁸⁹ but also new issues arising from the use of deepfakes and synthetic media with the intention of manipulating or deceiving XR users,¹⁹⁰ like “overlay attacks” (i.e. overlays unwanted content on a user's VR overview), “chaperone attacks” (i.e. modifies the VR user experience), “disorientation attacks” (i.e. cause dizziness and confusion), “human joystick attack” (i.e. control the immersed user's physical movement against their will), and “man-in-the-room attack” (i.e. infiltrate a chat room).¹⁹¹

EU cybersecurity framework is generally applicable to XR providers, which includes the NIS2 Directive and ePrivacy Directive, among others. XR-based entities, particularly those that offer services that include online marketplaces or social networking services, could be subject to the obligations of the NIS2 Directive, including, but not limited to, taking appropriate and proportionate technical, operational and

¹⁸¹ n (71), p. 150.

¹⁸² European Commission, *Call for Evidence and Public Consultation on the Forthcoming Digital Fairness Act* (Consultation document, COM, 17 July 2025) <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/consultations/commission-launches-open-consultation-forthcoming-digital-fairness-act> accessed 25 August 2025.

¹⁸³ n (71), p. 151.

¹⁸⁴ See n (1) S 7.2.3.

¹⁸⁵ European Commission, *Study on the Impact of Recent Developments in Digital Advertising on Privacy, Publishers and Advertisers* (2023) 233.

¹⁸⁶ Article 6(5), DMA.

¹⁸⁷ Article 6(6), DMA.

¹⁸⁸ Recital 8, UCPD.

¹⁸⁹ n (63), para 6.

¹⁹⁰ Mohammed El-Hajj, ‘Cybersecurity and Privacy Challenges in Extended Reality: Threats, Solutions, and Risk Mitigation Strategies’ (2025) 4(1) *Virtual Worlds* 1, doi:10.3390/virtualworlds4010001 accessed 25 August 2025.

¹⁹¹ See n (2) S 7.2.

organisational measures to manage cybersecurity risks,¹⁹² notification of significant incidents to authorities, and information of those incidents to users.¹⁹³ However, the NIS2 Directive does not deal with cybersecurity requirements for those companies within the XR ecosystem that provide software that is not included in the list of covered entities, as well as the manufacturers of headsets and handsets.¹⁹⁴

One of the main objectives of the ePrivacy Directive is that providers of publicly available electronic communications services take appropriate technical and organisational measures to safeguard the security of its services.¹⁹⁵ This directive also comes with obligations of notifying authorities and subscribers in case of a data breach. However, the applicability of the ePrivacy Directive is very limited to XR, given that in most cases communication features are purely ancillary features (e.g. a chat in a VR game) and thus they do not fall into the definition of 'electronic communication services'.

As seen in our previous work, both the NIS2 Directive and the ePrivacy Directive have a very limited impact on XR technologies. A solution to this lack of norms could be to extend the scope of the covered entities under the NIS2 Directive to other XR providers that, because of the immersiveness of the technology, can cause different impact not only to important sectors but also to users.

4.5. Impact on democracy and political manipulation

The combination of some of the previous challenges – high use of personal data and deceptive practices – are the base for the proliferation of disinformation and manipulation with political goals. Such challenge already exists in social media platforms, but given the immersive nature of XR technologies, it could reach new levels of effectiveness.¹⁹⁶

The EU regulatory framework generally applicable to deceptive practices – comprehended by the UCPD, GDPR, and DSA – may already help tackling these issues in an XR environment. In particular, the DSA has provided the basis for the adoption of voluntary codes of conduct following the recognition by the EC.¹⁹⁷ One of the codes that has been integrated into the DSA framework is the 2022 Strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation,¹⁹⁸ which has been signed by 42 companies or online platforms,¹⁹⁹ some of them providers of XR services (e.g. Meta and Google), but their signatures were done only on behalf of their services designated as VLOPs under the DSA (none of them being an XR-focused platform). Additionally, while the DSA includes important provisions to combat illegal content, such as hate speech or incitement to violence, the problems of disinformation and fake news generally do not fall under the definition of "illegal content" in most Member States. As a result, the obligation to address such content arises only under Article 34 DSA, through risk mitigation measures required of VLOPs. XR platforms not designated as VLOPs are therefore not subject to these obligations, leaving a regulatory gap in the context of immersive disinformation.

¹⁹² Art. 21(2), NIS2 Directive.

¹⁹³ Art. 23, NIS2 Directive.

¹⁹⁴ See n(2) S 7.2.

¹⁹⁵ Article 4, ePrivacy Directive

¹⁹⁶ See n(1) S 12.1.4 and XR4Human, D2.2 S 3.2.3.4.

¹⁹⁷ Article 45, DSA

¹⁹⁸ European Commission, *2022 Strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation* (European Commission, June 2022)

¹⁹⁹ European Commission, *Signatories of the 2022 Strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation* (Digital Strategy – European Commission, 16 June 2022) <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/signatories-2022-strengthened-code-practice-disinformation> accessed 25 August 2025.

Moreover, the DSA explicitly prohibits general monitoring obligations, which, while intended to safeguard fundamental rights such as freedom of expression and privacy, may inadvertently constrain the ability of XR providers to proactively identify and remove harmful political manipulation or coordinated influence operations. Given the unique characteristics of XR content, which can involve real-time spatial interactions, biometric feedback, and personalized sensory cues, traditional content moderation models are ill-suited for immersive environments.

The new Regulation on the transparency and targeting of political advertising,²⁰⁰ applicable from October 2025, aims to regulate political advertising services outside the scope of the DSA, and covers “online platforms, websites, mobile applications, computer games and other digital interfaces”,²⁰¹ which includes the different formats used by VR and AR platforms. This regulation will add transparency obligations for online political advertisements involving the processing of personal data, and focuses on ‘targeting or amplification techniques’ in such context. In addition, the initiative “European Democracy Shield” created by the EC to address the increasing threats to democratic institutions, systems and processes within the EU, could be a good forum to address the impact of immersive technologies to the democratic framework.²⁰²

²⁰⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/900 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 March 2024 on the transparency and targeting of political advertising <http://data.europa.eu/eli/req/2024/900/oj> accessed 25 August 2025.

²⁰¹ Recital 2, Regulation 2024/900.

²⁰² European Commission, *Have your say – Public consultations: ‘European Democracy Shield’* (Better Regulation, Initiative 14587, 2025) https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14587-European-Democracy-Shield_en accessed 25 August 2025.

5. Recommendations

Based on the challenges analysed in this report, we propose reviewing and clarifying the application of the EU legal framework to XR technologies. Please consider this section as a policy roadmap rather than a strict legal assessment, since the legislative techniques required to achieve the same result may differ upon closer examination.

This set of recommendations involves various stakeholders, including the European Parliament (EP) for the legal reform of EU regulations and directives, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) for the judicial interpretation of such regulations and directives, the European Commission (EC) for its delegated legislative and interpretative powers (including its subdivisions, e.g. the AI Office), Member States for the implementation of directives, and other authorities such as the European Data Protection Board (EDPB).

5.1. Clarify application of regulations to XR technologies

As demonstrated in our report, there are numerous regulations and directives that may be pertinent to XR technologies. However, in certain instances, the scope of such EU laws may be ambiguous. The achievement of this objective may be facilitated by the interpretation of the CJEU or a legislative initiative by the EP.

5.1.1. Clarify the application of the GPSR to XR devices

Targets: Physical injuries and accidents; Cybersickness.

In order to clarify whether risks of ergonomic stressors (such as physical strain from prolonged headset use or poor posture design), cognitive overload (such as disorientation, visual fatigue or cybersickness resulting from immersive environments) and spatial dissociation (such as accidents or injuries resulting from impaired awareness of the physical surroundings while using XR devices) are included in the concept of a 'safe product' under Article 3(1) GPSR, clarification is needed. The EC already considered this a priority in its "2020 Report on AI, IoT, and Robotics",²⁰³ which expressly recognized that mental and cognitive safety risks, especially for vulnerable users, must be addressed by product safety legislation.

Further clarification is required to determine whether integrated XR systems that combine physical hardware with real-time, sensory-driven software fall within the scope of the GPSR. XR hardware and software are not usually designed to function independently; rather, they operate as a convergent system in which the physical devices are inseparable from the immersive digital content, such as AR overlays, real-time spatial audio or AI-generated environments. In such scenarios, product safety cannot be assessed in isolation, but must be evaluated based on the interaction between the user, the device and the digital environment. Risk assessments must therefore account for potential harms arising from this interplay between hardware and software, such as visual overlays obscuring obstacles, delayed

²⁰³ n(5).

haptic feedback causing injury and spatial misalignment creating fall risks. This approach would reduce legal uncertainty for manufacturers and market surveillance authorities, while ensuring that consumers are adequately protected against the unique risks arising from embodied digital technologies.

5.1.2. Clarify application of the PLD and the Machine Regulation to XR devices

Targets: Long-lasting consequential impairments and impacts; Physical injuries and accidents.

The concept of a 'defective product' under Article 7 of the PLD could be reviewed through court interpretation or legal reform to clarify whether design choices leading to cumulative or long-term harm, even in the absence of traditional malfunctions or immediate injuries, fall within its scope. XR devices, including head-mounted displays, haptic wearables and immersive smart interfaces, introduce novel forms of risk that emerge from prolonged and repetitive use. Poor ergonomic design, such as imbalanced weight distribution, displays that induce eye strain, or interfaces that constrain posture, can lead to chronic musculoskeletal strain, visual fatigue, or psychological distress over time. While these harms may not arise from a technical 'defect' in the conventional sense, they are foreseeable consequences of negligent or suboptimal design. The current framework focuses too narrowly on immediate impacts, overlooking foreseeable long-term impacts, including physical and psychological harm. Adopting this interpretation would align the PLD with its stated purpose of ensuring fair compensation for consumers, while also reflecting the realities of modern wearable and immersive technology ecosystems, where long-term physical interaction with the body and senses is an integral part of how the product is used. The EC will need to evaluate this issue as part of the PLD evaluation required by Article 20 PLD by 2030.

It is also necessary to clarify whether XR devices featuring haptic feedback, motion sensors, mechanical actuation or integrated mechanical components fall within the scope of the Machinery Regulation. These features may constitute 'integrated machinery', as defined by the Regulation, which would trigger compliance obligations, including CE marking, risk assessment and essential health and safety requirements. Such clarification would ensure that immersive devices with mechanical or kinetic interfaces, such as VR head-mounted displays, exoskeletons and force-feedback gloves, are properly regulated for mechanical safety. This would bridge the conventional gap between digital product safety, ergonomics and physical risk, as outlined under the GPSR.

5.1.3. Clarify status of XR hardware as medical device

Target: Use and handling of XR hardware in healthcare.

XR technologies are often developed for consumer use, such as entertainment, education and gaming. However, they are increasingly being repurposed for clinical applications, including immersive relaxation apps, physical rehabilitation and exposure therapy for PTSD and phobias. In such cases, while the hardware itself is not intended for medical use, its functional application may fulfil the criteria for a medical purpose, creating legal uncertainty regarding its regulation under the MDR. In this context, it is important to clarify whether consumer-grade XR technologies used in clinical environments can be considered 'medical devices' under the MDR, despite not being designed for this purpose. Currently, there is legal ambiguity over whether these repurposed devices meet the MDR's definition of a 'medical device', particularly when their original intended purpose was not medical. This leads to regulatory gaps in risk classification, clinical oversight and safety assessment for XR devices.

5.1.4. Encourage adoption of safety standards

Article 7(1) of the GPSR states that a product is considered safe if it complies with 'relevant European standards' published in the Official Journal of the EU. In this context, the EC may support the development of voluntary standards for XR devices and immersive environments through European standardisation organisations such as CEN and CENELEC.

Such voluntary standards can address specific physical, spatial, and cognitive safety concerns that are not yet clearly defined by current product safety legislation. They may include guidelines on optimal weight distribution, headset strapping mechanisms and load-bearing thresholds to reduce strains to the neck, shoulders and back; minimum technical specifications for display refresh rates, resolution, brightness and field of view to reduce visual fatigue and motion sickness; and standardised safety protocols such as time-based breaks, lockout prompts or in-device fatigue detection to prevent overexposure. The establishment of such voluntary standards can serve multiple objectives, including providing clear, measurable benchmarks for compliance with product safety obligations under the GPSR; helping manufacturers to integrate safety-by-design principles into XR hardware development; facilitating market surveillance and risk assessment by national authorities through uniform technical criteria; and enhancing consumer trust and reducing the likelihood of injuries or long-term health effects.

5.2. Ensure GDPR compliance of XR-processed data

XR headsets can collect large amounts of data from users, most of which qualifies as personal data under the GDPR. Therefore, the GDPR generally applies to XR products and services, and XR providers must adhere to the regulation's principles. However, there is less consensus on the applicability of the GDPR to specific types of data, such as soft biometric data, emotional data, and bystanders' data. We propose including or clarifying the regulation of such types of data via legal reform and guidance from the EDPB.

5.2.1. Soft biometrics

Targets: Large-scale collection of personal data; Biometric and other sensitive data processing.

Under the GDPR, data containing physical, physiological or behavioural characteristics is recognised as biometric data only if it constitutes personal data (i.e. if it allows or confirms the unique identification of an individual). This means that non-identifying biometric data (or 'soft' biometrics) is outside the scope of the GDPR, even though processing it could affect users' privacy and data protection rights.²⁰⁴

Given the importance of this type of data for XR providers, we recommend that the EDPB issue guidelines on the regulation of soft biometrics. This guidance would not only be relevant for the XR ecosystem, but also for providers and users of AI systems. An alternative to technologically neutral guidance could be specific guidance on data processing techniques used by XR equipment, following the example of

²⁰⁴ n(52)

guidance on blockchain technologies currently under discussion.²⁰⁵ EDPB guidance will be essential in providing XR providers with clear rules for processing soft biometrics and other non-personal data.

Another way to address this regulatory gap, albeit less likely given the deregulation trends with regard to the GDPR, is to reform this regulation to explicitly address soft biometrics. One reform proposal is to expand the definition of biometric data under Article 3(34) of the GDPR to include soft biometrics²⁰⁶. This could be achieved by removing the requirement for biometric data to be used 'for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person'. Another proposal is to amend Article 9 of the GDPR, which currently classifies 'hard' biometrics as a special category of personal data, to include soft biometrics as an additional type of data that is specially protected under the GDPR.²⁰⁷ This could be achieved by including specific types of soft biometrics, such as keystroke, gait or voice modulation analysis, as sensitive data.

5.2.2. Emotion data

Targets: Large-scale collection of personal data; User targeting and emotional manipulation.

Emotion data has a similar status to soft biometrics in that it is not considered personal data per se, since it does not necessarily lead to the identification of an individual. When it does lead to identification, it is not included in the comprehensive list of special categories of data under Article 9 of the GDPR. To better protect XR users, given the considerable risk of such data being used for manipulation, we propose that Article 9 of the GDPR is also expanded to include emotion data. Guidance from the EDPB would also be welcome, whether it is general advice on the status of emotion data under the GDPR or focused on its specific use by XR technologies.

5.2.3. Bystanders' personal data

Targets: Large-scale collection of personal data; Bystanders' personal data collection.

XR providers need to comply with GDPR provisions for processing bystanders' personal data, particularly with regard to enabling them to exercise their data subject rights. Therefore, we believe that the EDPB should publish guidelines on processing bystanders' personal data using XR technologies. Although there is some previous advice on similar technologies (particularly on video cameras)²⁰⁸, and some suggestions could be applied to XR devices, we believe that the document does not seem suited to XR. This is not only

²⁰⁵ European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 02/2025 on processing of personal data through blockchain technologies* (adopted 14 April 2025) https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2025/guidelines-022025-processing-personal-data_en accessed 29 August 2025. Ellen O'Regan, 'Europe's GDPR Privacy Law Is Headed for Red Tape Bonfire within "Weeks" *Politico* (3 April 2025) <https://www.politico.eu/article/eu-gdpr-privacy-law-europe-president-ursula-von-der-leyen/> accessed 29 August 2025.

²⁰⁶ n(52)

²⁰⁷ Vinders J and Howkins B, *Enhancing EU legal frameworks for Digital Extended Reality* (TechEthos Project Deliverable 6.2 for the European Commission, 28 February 2023) <https://www.techethos.eu/enhancing-eu-legal-frameworks-digital-extended-reality/> accessed 29 August 2025.

²⁰⁸ European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 3/2019 on processing of personal data through video devices* (Version 2.0, adopted 29 January 2020) https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/guidelines/guidelines-32019-processing-personal-data-through-video_en accessed 29 August 2025.

because of the differences in technology and use cases, but also because the document is outdated, since there is no mention to the potential use of integrated AI.

5.3. Address user manipulation on XR platforms

As demonstrated in our research, deceptive practices can be amplified by the immersive nature of XR technologies. It is therefore recommended that certain regulations explicitly address user manipulation in XR technologies as a distinct case, or at the very least, provide clarification as to whether they fall within the scope of such regulations. This would serve to ensure a level playing field for both XR providers and users.

5.3.1. Definition of deceptive practices on XR platforms

Targets: Deceptive practices and unfair competition; Addiction, isolation and other psychosocial risks.

In order to ensure legal clarity, it is recommended that the UCPD Annex I listing of blacklisted unfair commercial practices be amended by the EP to explicitly reference immersive or XR-specific manipulative interfaces. Examples of such practices that may be subject to blacklisting include: (i) haptics-based coercion, or using tactile feedback to pressure users into purchasing or consenting; (ii) immersive dark patterns, or spatial design choices that obscure exit points or mislead users into unwanted actions, and (iii) forced immersion, or forcing users to stay in immersive environments without clear, accessible options to opt out. This amendment has the potential to ensure that regulators and courts can effectively identify and sanction unfair XR business practices, thereby aligning XR consumer protection with traditional digital markets.

A more likely alternative to a reform of the UCPD is for the EC to exercise its supervisory role under the DSA by issuing guidance on how dark patterns manifest in XR environments. This guidance could provide concrete examples of the aforementioned immersive dark patterns, offer XR platform providers recommendations on how to detect and prevent manipulative design, and suggest monitoring mechanisms to enable authorities to audit XR platforms and enforce transparency. Additionally, such guidance could clarify the specific effects of XR platform design, such as addictive design, as recommended by the EP's 2023 "Resolution on addictive design of online services and consumer protection"²⁰⁹. By providing such tailored guidance, the EC will empower regulators, platform operators and developers to uphold consumer protection standards in the rapidly evolving context of XR.

Finally, we recommend that the upcoming Digital Fairness Act includes a dedicated section that addresses manipulative practices unique to XR environments. Immersive environments allow for new forms of user manipulation that are not adequately covered by current consumer protection legislation. The Act should include specific provisions defining XR-specific manipulative behaviours, such as exploiting immersive sensory inputs (visual, auditory and haptic) to unduly influence user decision-making; utilising immersive ads or notifications that interrupt or manipulate the user experience; and

²⁰⁹ European Parliament, *Addictive design of online services and consumer protection in the EU single market* (Own-initiative report A9-0340/2023, adopted 12 December 2023) (https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2023-0340_EN.html) accessed 29 August 2025.

employing behavioural nudges in spatial interfaces that limit meaningful user consent. By codifying these behaviours, the Digital Fairness Act can establish clear legal boundaries against unfair manipulation in XR environments, thereby safeguarding consumer rights.

5.3.2. Better enforcement of the legal framework on XR platforms

Targets: Deceptive practices and unfair competition; Harmful behaviour, offensive and violent interactions; Inauthentic identities and deepfakes; Cybersecurity vulnerabilities.

It is recommended that content moderation obligations under the DSA and AVMSD be strengthened through the evaluation of detection and reporting mechanisms for deepfake identity fraud. Furthermore, the EU cybersecurity framework should categorise deepfake identity fraud as a high-risk digital crime, thereby ensuring that scams facilitated by deepfake technology and identity theft are subject to legal repercussions under international cybercrime legislation.

Another way to ensure that these technologies remain fit for the future is to review the GPSR, with a view to encourage security measures against biometric spoofing in XR hardware. This will prevent biometric authentication mechanisms (i.e. iris scanning or facial recognition) from being easily bypassed by deepfake-generated identities. The standardisation of hardware-level authentication protocols has the potential to enhance the cybersecurity protections across XR platforms, thereby mitigating the risk of identity fraud in immersive digital environments.

5.3.3. Promote literacy about XR-related risks and child protection

Targets: Digital literacy, access and affordability; Children and other vulnerable users.

The AVMSD currently requires Member States to encourage the development of media literacy skills among the public, particularly with regard to audiovisual content (Article 33a). However, XR systems, such as VR environments, AR overlays and MR simulations, are increasingly being used for news, entertainment, advertising and education, and pose new challenges that go beyond those of traditional media formats. The EC may therefore consider issuing a new communication to encourage Member States to extend the scope of national media literacy initiatives to explicitly include an understanding of the persuasive and immersive effects of XR experiences. This would cover simulated reality and identity manipulation, awareness of privacy risks and data profiling, psychological immersion in XR content and the ability to distinguish between real and synthetic experiences – especially in the context of XR's use in journalism, advertising or political communication.

These initiatives would protect vulnerable users, especially children, from misinformation, manipulation and unsafe social experiences in immersive environments, while fostering informed digital citizenship. However, we believe that more can be done in this regard, including the EC issuing guidelines on the online protection of minors on XR platforms (Article 28(3) of the DSA), and special measures for XR platforms being incorporated into the upcoming EU Code of Conduct on age-appropriate design²¹⁰.

²¹⁰ European Commission, *Special group on the EU Code of conduct on age-appropriate design* (Shaping Europe's digital future, last updated 5 May 2025) <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/group-age-appropriate-design> accessed 29 August 2025.

5.3.4. Address immersive political manipulation

Target: Impact on democracy and political manipulation.

The upcoming Regulation on Political Advertising should explicitly cover immersive political advertisement delivered via XR technologies. This includes but is not limited to VR-based political rallies, town halls, or candidate appearances, AR overlays promoting political messages or campaign materials in public or private spaces, or MR experiences designed to influence voter perceptions or engagement.

5.4. Address enhanced risks of XR-AI integration

AI technologies are used in XR platforms and virtual worlds to improve personalisation, make interfaces more intuitive, and generate virtual spaces, objects, and subjects. While this brings benefits, it also poses challenges to the XR environment. Many of the challenges described in this report for XR technologies could be exacerbated by integration with AI. This is where the implementation of the AI Act plays a pivotal role in the future of XR technologies. We propose the following actions:

5.4.1. Classifying AI-powered XR systems as high-risk

Targets: User targeting and emotional manipulation; Use and handling of XR hardware in healthcare.

The EC may consider leveraging its delegated powers to generally classify immersive AI-powered XR systems as high-risk AI systems under Article 6(2) AI Act, either through delegated legislation regarding Annex III under Article 7 AI Act or by evaluation under Article 112 AI Act. This move would formalize the regulation of AI systems whose immersive sensory interaction creates heightened risks. Immersive AI functionalities, such as AI-enabled agents and avatars, voice-cloning technology, or emotion-aware simulations, can interact directly with a user's perception and body. Even when not used in traditional high-risk AI sectors, they can cause significant psychological, cognitive, or physical harm. Incorporating immersive AI systems into the "high-risk" category or formally recognizing them via guidance would ensure the Act remains effective and future-proof in an increasingly embodied digital landscape.

In addition, the EC may consider issuing guidance or interpretative documents under the AI Act to clarify that a "significant risk of harm", as referenced in the context of high-risk AI systems²¹¹, explicitly includes psychological and mental health-related harms, particularly those arising from extended or immersive interaction with XR-based AI systems. Immersive environments powered by AI such as adaptive virtual therapy platforms, biometric emotion-recognition systems, or AI-driven avatars, can deeply influence users' cognitive and emotional states. This is especially relevant where XR systems are used in sensitive applications, including healthcare, education, behavioural nudging, or workplace monitoring. Prolonged exposure to emotionally manipulative, overstimulating, or immersive content may lead to cognitive overload, psychological distress, or even breakdowns and suicidal tendencies, particularly among vulnerable users such as adolescents, individuals with pre-existing mental health conditions, or persons

²¹¹ Article 6(3) AI Act.

in high-pressure training environments. This interpretation would also support consistency with broader EU digital safety and consumer protection strategies, including the DSA and the Mental Health Strategy launched under the EU Health Union, which looks to addressing mental health across all policies.²

5.4.2. Clarify the role of XR technologies in AI-driven emotion recognition

Targets: Invasive uses in the workplace and education; User targeting and emotional manipulation.

The AI Act prohibits the use of AI systems to infer emotions of a natural person in the areas of workplace and education institutions, except where the use of the AI system is intended to be put in place or into the market for medical or safety reasons.²¹² Since XR devices can accumulate biometric and emotional data which can be processed in a way that provides deep knowledge of, or inference about, an individual's actions, perceptions and emotions. These features could then be used for an impromptu assessment in schools or workplaces, depending on the purpose that providers and deployers give to an AI system integrated into a XR software. As such, specific guidelines are needed to clearly disassociate emotion recognition applications from XR devices used in education and workplace. It is our understanding that XR hardware manufacturers should not be held responsible if the device itself is not intended to monitor individuals, and the responsibility should be assigned to the software/platform provider.

5.4.3. Encourage development of codes of conduct under the AI Act

An alternative proposal is that the EC through its AI Office (under Article 95) supports the development of voluntary "Safety-by-Design" codes of conduct for non-high-risk systems which are tailored to XR technologies. These voluntary but structured codes should offer detailed implementation guidance to developers of XR systems, particularly where AI-driven features influence user cognition, perception, or physical interaction with the environment.

Given the intense sensory immersion and real-world detachment involved in XR, these systems pose unique challenges to user autonomy, safety, and mental health. These codes can include provisions for mandatory "panic buttons" or quick-exit mechanisms that allow users to immediately disengage from the immersive environment in case of distress, confusion, or emergency, real-world override features, mandatory human oversight for critical XR applications, including those used in mental health, education, workplace monitoring, or high-pressure training environments, or built-in usage time limits or fatigue-detection prompts to prevent overexposure and cognitive exhaustion. Such codes would not only support compliance with fundamental rights and user safety principles under the AI Act (including transparency, accountability, and human oversight), but could also serve as a foundation for future standardization efforts through CEN/CENELEC.

²¹² Article 5(1)(f) AI Act

6. Conclusions

The development of XR technologies is fast even though it might not be as rapid as many foresaw in the past twenty years. The embedment of XR in everyday life is taking place at a slow but steady rate. Entertainment is the main field of technological expansion, while health, training and education are also upcoming fields. Every field contains its own challenges, sensitivities and specialised regulatory arena. In addition, the advent of AI has created a new level of deliberations that penetrates all XR applications. It is in this context that our work took place.

Our analysis has been comprehensive in terms of the breadth of regulations that formed our main research focus. After the first review on policy debates (D3.1) it was evident that XR represents a series of enabling technologies that can potentially be applied in every field of societal functions. From finance to entertainment, health, work, or education, XR applications show great potential that also brings about great challenges. In order to figure out whether the current European legislative landscape can deal with these challenges, we performed a gap analysis of twenty-six European regulations and directives on privacy and data, intellectually property, consumer and competition law, media and online services, cybersecurity, accessibility and non-discrimination, sectoral law, technology law, and finance law (D3.2). Our results indicated the need for policy action that formed the content of this final report.

The identification of the regulatory gaps and our recommendations cover the full range of XR functions and fields of applications. Physical effects caused by the use of XR devices (including injuries and accidents), use of XR devices and software in healthcare, privacy and data security (including soft biometric), bystander data, deception and manipulation, use of XR by children, and the use of AI in XR applications, have all formed the core of the policy recommendations that we offer here. Our work is not only oriented to policy makers. Although regulatory structures are technical matters that must be voted in by politicians, our view is that stakeholder involvement (including both CSOs and industry) is crucial for effective and social sustainable regulations. As such, our recommendations refer to a policy roadmap that ought to initiate widespread debates on how to deal with the current XR challenges and opportunities. We view this as a necessary step to ensure a human-centric XR development that our project has set out to achieve.

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